

The Kids Are Alright Creating and Managing Lasting Greenspace in Schools

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Master thesis presented in fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of
Master of Science in Urban Studies (VUB) and Master of Science in Geography,
general orientation, track 'Urban Studies' (ULB)

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Creating and Managing Lasting Greenspaces in Schools

A Masters Thesis by Kate Amber
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Cover Image: Green-Blue Schoolyard, Rotterdam (own picture)

“We could never have loved the earth so well if we had had no childhood in it”

George Eliot,
The Mill on the Floss

Acknowledgment

Researching and writing this thesis has been an extraordinary journey – challenging, inspiring and deeply fulfilling. What began in the fourth grade, when a few friends and I advocated to transform an empty corner of our schoolyard into a garden, has blossomed into the privilege of contributing to a project like Opération Ré-création. I'm immensely grateful to the teachers who generously shared their valuable time with me, and to the children who shared their wisdom and enthusiasm. My sincere thanks also go to everyone from Brussels Environment, 21 Solutions, ARTER, Tournesol-Zonnebloem, and others who took the time to speak with me along the way.

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Abstract

Opération Ré-création (OR) is a transformative initiative led by Brussels Environment (BE) to convert 19 schoolyards across Brussels into greenspaces by 2025, setting a precedent for future urban greening efforts. This research evaluates the project's participatory design process and examines how expectations and responsibilities were managed between schools and stakeholders by emphasizing successful strategies and identifying challenges. The study also explores the long-term management and educational use of the green schoolyards. The findings highlight the project's success in fostering a participatory design approach, giving children a meaningful role in shaping their environment. However, it also identifies areas for improvement and adaptation in future phases. The research underscores the importance of maintaining children's voices at the heart of the green schoolyard movement to foster a deeper connection to nature and drive broader community engagement. The findings aim to inform future efforts in urban sustainability and set a precedent for future green initiatives, showcasing Opération Ré-création as a noteworthy experiment in transforming urban school environments

I. Introduction

As cities confront the challenges of climate change, innovative initiatives are emerging to adapt urban spaces to evolving conditions offering a chance to rethink traditional cityscapes. The urgent need to build resilient cities opens the door to simultaneous, transformative social changes – not just in how we design physical spaces but also in how these spaces shape our behaviors, thoughts, and daily lives. Children, who are particularly vulnerable to climate-related issues such as heat stress and air pollution, stand to be significantly impacted by these adaptations. Children represent a key demographic for change, with the potential to reshape environmental habits, challenge conventional views on climate, and improve overall health from a young age. Green schoolyards present a powerful opportunity to address climate change, reimagine urban landscapes, and reduce climate stressors for children while fostering a deeper connection to the environment. In recent years, many cities have increasingly embraced schoolyard greening projects, a movement that has not only gained significant momentum but also sparked a broader rethinking of urban design.

In Brussels, Opération Ré-création (OR) represents a pioneering initiative transforming 19 schoolyards into green havens. Spearheaded by Brussels Environment (BE), the city's environmental agency, OR serves as a pilot project, exploring innovative strategies within the broader context of similar initiatives in other capital cities. The initial phase, involving the 19 schools, is scheduled for completion by 2025, with plans to extend the project to an additional six schools in a subsequent iteration. This progression provides an opportunity to critically assess and refine the initial round of schoolyard transformations, offering valuable insights into potential challenges and best practices.

Over the past 18 months, this research delved into Opération Ré-création by conducting school visits, interviews, and a thorough review of relevant literature. The goal is to unravel the layers to illuminate the project's complexity by exploring its diverse stakeholders, strategies, and outcomes, all within Belgium's complex political and linguistic landscape. At its core, this research asks, *what are the variables in the long-term viability of green schoolyards, and how can these factors be utilized to optimize long-term success?*

The study begins with an evaluation of progress made to date in the co-creation process and early stages of construction by addressing two key questions:

- 1) *How were expectations set and responsibilities communicated between the schools and other partners during the co-creation phase?*

2) How was the feedback from the co-creation process translated into a strategic plan and implemented in the final product?

Looking ahead, the research also considers future needs by posing two additional questions:

3) What key knowledge and skills do schools need to effectively manage and maintain their schoolyard?

4) How can the integration of the schoolyard into educational practices and community partnerships enhance its potential for broader impact?

To address these questions, the research synthesizes existing literature on the green schoolyard movement, participatory design, maintenance practices, pedagogical use, and community compact. It incorporates insights from interviews with teachers, students, parents, Brussels Environment representatives, and other stakeholders involved in Opération Ré-création. This comprehensive analysis aims to present a detailed overview of the project's evolution, spotlight successful strategies, and identify challenges to inform future efforts.

II. *Literature Review*

2.1 An Introduction to Green Schoolyards

Urbanization profoundly reshaped the urban childhood experience, now increasingly marked by a sedentary, indoor lifestyle, sequestered from the natural world. This shift can be attributed to several factors, including a stark reduction in open and accessible greenspaces in cities, and heightened safety concerns, limiting opportunities for independent and unsupervised outdoor play.

The development of urban areas has significantly diminished accessible greenspaces, including backyards and open streets, limiting children's opportunities to experience a sense of freedom and discovery through unrestricted play (Cunningham et al., 2002; Dowdell et al., 2011). Historically, children engaged with open, undefined spaces shaping their environment to suit their needs and desires (Chawla, 2015, p. 433). Today, children rarely spend time outside of places specifically designed for them, which tend to be overly structured, "bland," and "uninteresting," often devoid of natural elements – a deliberate choice aimed at minimizing maintenance efforts, and avoiding legal liabilities (Cunningham et al., p. 11, 2002). Roger Hart's observation of children in New York City highlighted the limitations of traditional playgrounds, which often restrict the creative exploration children long for (Bartlett, 2002).

Even when children have the possibility to play in local parks or streets, or walk themselves to school, growing fears about traffic, strangers, and the natural environment further restrict their mobility and independence, contributing to sedentary lifestyles, largely confined to supervised settings (Gilchrist, et al., 2017). Social pressures on well-intentioned parents, reinforce a culture of risk aversion, with additional fear of judgment or reproach for allowing children unsupervised access to their surroundings (Rooney, 2017; Malone & Tranter, 2003). This phenomenon is compounded by urban inequalities, as children in less affluent neighborhoods frequently have limited access to greenspace, fewer opportunities to engage with the natural environment, and face heightened safety concerns (Baró et al., 2021).

These factors contribute to a growing "nature deficit" among children, (Gilchrist, et al., 2017, p. 106; Vidal and Castro Seixas, 2022), which when coupled with risk-averse restrictions, can impact their physical and emotional development (Rooney, 2017). The importance of play cannot be overstated; it is described as "the work of childhood" (Cunningham et al., 2002). Tranter and Malone (2004) emphasize play as "justified purely on the basis that it is fun: children enjoy it," describing its critical role in fostering intelligence and self-sufficiency later in life (p. 153). Jenks (2005), further suggests that the

“process of insulation” and resulting boredom children experience in sanitized environments may seem trivial, but can have profound long-term implications for their problem-solving abilities and self-confidence (Rooney, 2017).

Concerns surrounding children’s interaction with nature often extend beyond safety and security, encompassing an aversion to the perceived messiness and unpredictability of nature play. Unfortunately, parents who harbor fears about the environment and restrict their children’s access to it may inadvertently perpetuate those fears, hindering the development of a positive relationship between their children and nature (Rooney, 2017). As Cunningham, et al. (2002) observes, amidst these fears the “central players in all this – the children – are apt to be forgotten” (p. 15).

Despite the well-documented benefits of greening schoolyards, many adults perceive such initiatives as inherently risky. Common concerns include the potential increased risk of injury, natural elements obstructing supervision, and the possibility for criminal activity (Bell and Dymont, 2008). In response to these fears, schools have increasingly adopted a culture of surveillance and prevention, further limiting children’s opportunities to engage in *risky play*, defined by Sandseter and Kennair (2011) as thrilling and adventurous play in the form of challenging physical activities which involve the potential risk of physical injury (Bell and Dymont, 2008). Risky play represents essential opportunities for children to rehearse potentially challenging experiences in the real world, developing a healthy understanding of risk by testing their limits, capacities, and comprehension of consequences – all while building self-confidence and trust with adults (Rooney, 2017; Sandseter and Kennair, 2011). Ellen Sandseter, a professor of early-childhood education, argues that risky play is “normal” for childhood and vital for preventing the development of phobias (Sandseter and Kennair, 2011, p. 258).

Many concerns surrounding risk are theoretical and often unsupported by empirical studies on risky play. For instance, Bell and Dymont (2008) found that in a study of 45 Canadian schools, greening resulted in fewer injuries, as the softened surfaces and natural elements slowed children’s movement. Despite the perceived risks, greened yards provide a higher quality of play and improved health outcomes by offering an alternative to the hyper-surveillance strategies that limit children’s freedom (Dijk-Wesselius et al., 2018). They represent a promising approach to counter the institutionalization of risk-aversion, ensuring that children can engage in and benefit from risky play.

To fully understand the significance of greening schoolyards, and the subsequent benefits, it is essential to distinguish between “places for children,” typically designed by adults for children, and “children’s places,” which are spaces children discover and appropriate for themselves (Rasmussen, 2004, p. 3 & 12). The loss of children’s places in urban

environments is directly linked to decreased activity levels and nature deficit experienced by children. Rasmussen's distinction also prompts us to consider the intention behind places for children, which often segregate young people into predefined spaces rather than allowing them to participate in creating spaces alongside adults.

Given that many places designated for children are not necessarily ones they would choose for themselves, researchers have increasingly sought to understand children's preferences, to develop an understanding of what can truly be considered children's places (Lekies et al., 2006). Kevin Lynch, as part of the 'Growing Up In Cities' project, found that the most frequently used spaces by children were "wastelands" – overgrown, wild areas that "evoked both attraction and fear," which most importantly, provided space for children to be alone or with friends, but nonetheless independent (Chawla, 2015, p. 436). Similarly, Titman (1994) found that children preferred natural environments over built ones, and Moore (1980) noted that children consistently cited a preference for nature areas (Chawla, 2015).

Play in greenspaces is less structured, more expressive and imaginative, with nature providing space for the endless ways children need to articulate themselves through play. Moore (1980) observed the significance of "rough ground" used as "adventure play" where children could modify their environment (Chawla, 2015, p. 437). Nicholson (1971), similarly discovered children spending time "alone quietly resting, watching or dabbling in sand or water," and learned from interviews how those moments represented "important retreats in times of trouble" (Chawla, 2015, p. 436).

Moore, Nicholson, and Hart, consistently observed children engaged in loose parts play with natural elements, defined by Nicholson's (1971) *Theory of Loose Parts*, as moveable components that offer abundant, open-ended, and flexible play opportunities. Their observations highlight the value of such play in enabling children to endlessly manipulate their environment by building structures, creating hiding spots, challenging their imaginations. Several researchers note how greened play spaces promote more varied and diverse forms of play, partially due to the presence of loose parts, fostering inclusivity among age, gender, and ability groups (Dowdell et al., 2011; Jansson et al., 2014; Dijk-Wesselius et al., 2018). Central to these activities is the sense of unsupervised independence, with Moore noting how nature play could "absorb the sometimes untidy results without attracting adults' ire" ([cited in] Chawla, 2015, p. 437). Hart underscores the importance of children learning about themselves through their environment by gaining knowledge and skills through challenges they adapt to their own level of competency (Chawla, 2015).

From these differences in play we can see the crucial need for children to have access to natural spaces despite urban densification minimizing unrestricted play areas. Greening schoolyards offers a viable solution by facilitating daily access to nature and addressing inequalities in access to greenspace (Baró et al., 2021). Schoolyards, usually evenly distributed across urban areas and representing spaces where children spend substantial time, are prime candidates for greening initiatives (Flax et al., 2020; Dijk-Wesselius et al., 2018; Dowdell et al., 2011). Flax, et al. (2020) argues that creating numerous smaller greenspaces within schoolyards creates “redundancy,” ensuring consistent access to greenspace even if certain initiatives don’t reach their full potential (p. 5). Integrating natural elements into an educational environment facilitates opportunities for informed, meaningful interactions with nature, enhancing play experiences and fostering a deeper environmental connection (Chawla, 1996; Palmer, 1993; Wilson, 1997).

Despite the well-documented benefits and urgent need for additional greenspace, many schoolyards remain monotonous, uninspiring, concrete fields. These areas are often perceived as ancillary to the primary educational activities within the school building, utilized as a space for kids to “blow off steam,” underestimating the value of outdoor play (Bagot, 2005, p. 15; Wilson, 1997). The lack of stimulation in these traditional schoolyards contributes to boredom among children, which can lead to increased conflicts, aggression, and physical inactivity (Malone & Tranter, 2003; Lucas & Dymont, 2010). The absence of imaginative play opportunities often results in either sedentary activities or dominance of ball games, which can monopolize available space (Tranter & Malone, 2004). Consequently, students frequently lack a strong sense of attachment to their schoolyard (Rasmussen, 2004).

At their best, schoolyards can serve as dynamic environments for both formal and informal learning, igniting children’s creativity, and reinforcing their connection to the school and natural world. Greening schoolyards also provides climate benefits extending beyond school grounds, such as enhancing flood mitigation, promoting biodiversity, reducing temperatures, improving air quality, and bolstering community resilience against climate change (Flax et al., 2020; Baró et al., 2022).

The school community also directly benefits from greening, including improvements in physical health, cognitive functioning, mental well-being, and more inclusive play opportunities. Students in schools with greened yards report reduced stress and anger, lower rates of depression, increased energy and happiness, and improved social and emotional skills (Baró et al., 2022; Chawla, 2015; Chawla et al., 2014; Dijk-Wesselius et al., 2018). Students frequently describe their green yards as “peaceful,” “calm,” “relaxing,” providing them with a sense of connectedness to the natural world (Chawla, 2015, p. 444; Chawla et al., 2014, p. 9).

Benefits from exposure to nature extend to cognitive functioning, including improved attention and focus (Bell & Dymont, 2008; Chawla, 2015; Dijk-Wesselius et al., 2018). Other cognitive advantages include enhanced imagination, creativity, awareness, reasoning, observational skills, and critical thinking (Dowdell et al., 2011; Dymont, 2005). Some studies even indicate that students in schools with gardens achieve higher grades and standardized test scores, and in one case, higher graduation rates (Blair, 2009; Chawla, 2015; Ernst & Monroe, 2004). Gardens also provide valuable alternative learning opportunities for students who struggle with traditional academics, offering possibilities to develop skills and improving self-esteem, while gaining peer respect (Lieberman & Hoody, 1998).

Physical health benefits include improved heat regulation through added shade, improved sleep, lower blood pressure, and healthier eating habits with access to a school garden (Bell & Dymont, 2008; Blair, 2009; Chawla et al., 2014; Chawla, 2015). One of the most frequently observed benefits is an increase in physical activity, particularly among girls. Researchers who tracked students on greened schoolyards found children taking a higher step count, and signs of improved motor fitness and balance (Bell & Dymont, 2008).

Traditional schoolyards often prioritize competitive sports and ball games, which occupy large areas for few students, and create social hierarchies based on a narrow vision of physical prowess, relegating students with less confidence and interest in their physical abilities, particularly girls, to the margins of the schoolyard (Tranter & Malone, 2004; Titman, 1994; Coen et al., 2019). Conversely, greened schoolyards offer diverse play options, promoting equitable participation across genders by creating more appropriate and appealing spaces for all students, encouraging physical activity for everyone (Brink et al., 2010; Bell & Dymont, 2008; Coen et al., 2019).

On greened schoolyards, kids can “expand their play repertoire” by exploring their environment through imaginary play by climbing on logs, jumping, and digging, inspiring less conventional forms of physical activity (Bell & Dymont, 2008; Lucas & Dymont, 2010, p. 183). Play is not only more varied on a green schoolyard, but play episodes are longer, more creative, and encourage students to participate cooperatively and harmoniously (Chawla, 2015; Chawla et al., 2014; Mårtensson et al., 2014; Lucas & Dymont, 2010). Research by Raney et al. (2019) demonstrated that following a greening project, students shifted from traditional ball games to more varied play activities such as tag, gymnastics, climbing and jumping, and creative play, with significant increases in participation from both girls and boys. Green schoolyards also provide valuable opportunities for solitude and personal space, contributing to a more balanced and inclusive play environment (Wilson, 1997).

2.2 Examples of Green Schoolyard Programs

In response to the urgency of climate change, many cities, including Brussels, are adopting schoolyard greening initiatives in their city-planning. These projects often prioritize the removal of impervious surfaces, and implement strategies aimed at alleviating heat stress and managing rainfall, alongside enhancing educational opportunities and expanding community access to greenspace.

The Oasis project in Paris exemplifies this approach, focusing on the progressive transformation of schoolyards by integrating shade and water features to regulate temperature, improve rainwater management, and increase vegetation. Additionally, the project seeks to tailor these environments to the needs of children (City of Paris, 2023). A notable aspect of the Oasis project is its commitment to community engagement, including the opening of schoolyards to the public on weekends, ensuring wide-spread community benefits. The renovated yards also serve as venues for outdoor learning, like educational gardens and outdoor classrooms. The transformation process involves collaborative design efforts with students and features participatory elements during construction, including planting workshops, small furniture construction, and pavement marking (CAUE de Paris). Since its inception in 2014, the project successfully transformed 131 schoolyards, with an ambitious target to green all 760 public schools by 2050 (City of Paris, 2023).

In Barcelona, Climate Shelters, *Refugis Climàtics*, and consecutively the *Transformem* program, have transformed 58 schoolyards to date. This initiative employs a multifaceted approach, integrating water management, shade, vegetation, and enhanced insulation to tackle heat and other climate-related challenges (Ajuntament de Barcelona-A). Similar to the Oasis project, this initiative emphasizes a participatory approach and community accessibility through the *Patis escolars oberts al barri* project. During public access hours, each yard is supervised by a monitor who opens and closes the yard at scheduled times and encourages engagement from all age groups (Ajuntament de Barcelona-B).

Many other cities are adopting projects with similar goals and strategies. In Madrid, the Care in School Environments program, *Cuidados en Entornos Escolares*, converted three schoolyards between 2017 and 2019, aiming to rejuvenate the educational and health impact of schoolyards, while incorporating participatory design strategies (Baró et al., 2022). Rotterdam's Green Blue Schoolyards, *Groen Blauwes Schoolpleinen*, transformed 40 yards to date, with ongoing applications (Gemeente Rotterdam). The municipality of Rotterdam supports these efforts by providing five annual subsidies of 80,000€, covering design, construction, management, and the organization of activities for neighborhood children (Gemeente Rotterdam).

2.3 Participatory Design

The emerging schoolyard greening initiatives employ a diverse array of strategies in their conceptualization and implementation, with a recurring emphasis on a participatory approach in their design. Specifically, these initiatives underscore the involvement of primary users – the children – in the design process. This trend aligns with a broader movement advocating for the inclusion of young people in decision-making and civic engagement. Traditionally, children are largely segregated from adult spheres, particularly in their capacity to influence their surroundings, rarely asked how their environment could be improved or changed, and often relegated to the role of passive observer or “citizens-in-waiting” (Cook, 2017, p. 445; Bartlett, 2002).

In school settings, children experience their environment in ways that are often more nuanced and personal than adults, so their perceptions and opinions hold more weight. Relying solely on adult perspectives – such as parents or teachers – presumes that these views accurately reflect those of the students (Cunningham et al., 2002). Such assumptions fail to distinguish between ‘children’s place’ and ‘places for children.’ While they can overlap, it’s evident that children need and want spaces that differ from those designed by adults for them (Rasmussen, 2004). Children possess a unique understanding of the “complexity and the nuances” of their environment, built on their first hand experiences (Tranter & Malone, 2004, p. 152; Rigolon, 2011). Moreover, children as young as three or four years old demonstrate their capacity “to voice opinions, provide unique knowledge, and contribute to improvements in outdoor play areas” (Lekies et al., 2006, p. 139). Their input brings “vital knowledge,” “fresh ideas and idealistic views” balanced with a realistic understanding of constraints (Rigolon, 2011, p. 153).

Inclusive participation enhances the long-term success of greening projects by fostering a sense of meaning attachment to space (Derr & Rigolon, 2017). Engaging the entire community, including children, cultivates a stronger sense of care and increased use of the space (Derr & Rigolon, 2017). By instilling a sense of ownership, children are more likely to take responsibility for their environment and be actively involved in its upkeep. Although a participative approach can be time-consuming and labor intensive, involving children is “the best investment for short-term results and for the long-term perspective” (Askew, 2019, p. 55).

Including students in the participative process not only benefits the school community but helps develop crucial skills related to democracy and citizenship (Dyment, 2008; Rigolon, 2011; Derr & Rigolon, 2017). Those skills carry over into adulthood, reinforcing civic engagement and active citizenry, fostering a sense of community and environmental stewardship (Dyment, 2008). Participation also enhances self-confidence, self-esteem, decision-making, communication, and goal-setting (Rigolon, 2011; Derr & Rigolon, 2017).

Overall, participatory design creates a platform for equal exchange and dialogue, facilitating mutual learning between adults and children.

Participatory design can take shape in a number of ways, including drawing, design games, and hands-on activities (Brink & Yost, 2004; Dymont, 2008, p. 8; Rigolon, 2011). Some schools utilize inspirational images, while others employ surveys or establish student councils to gather ideas from students, which inform a master plan (Brink & Yost, 2004; Dymont, 2008). Regardless of the specific approach, an educational phase preceding design activities is crucial for establishing a shared understanding of project goals and constraints, thereby fostering creativity beyond conventional design paradigms (Zltus & Hart, 1994).

Hart (1997) commends the inclusion of children in design and planning as “laudable” but underscores the significant losses incurred when students are excluded from problem identification (Dymont, 2008, p. 10). This observation prompts a critical examination of how to avoid token participation and ensure genuine involvement of children. Rigolon (2011) advocates for a holistic participatory approach that integrates children and adults, ensuring opinions and thoughts are equally considered, creating an open and accessible process with clearly defined roles (p. 154).

2.4 Maintenance

Moving towards the implementation of green schoolyards, maintenance presents a consistent challenge for schools as they navigate the use and care of their transformed yard (Giezen & Pellerey, 2021). A study of schools with gardens in Los Angeles found that 14 percent failed to maintain their greenspaces effectively (Ozer, 2007). Like participatory design approaches, involving students in maintenance efforts can foster a deeper sense of place and pride within the school community (Titman, 1994). When greenspaces are not adequately maintained, children can experience confusion, interpreting the neglect of the garden as reflective of the schools care of the students themselves (Titman, 1994).

The participatory design phase is closely linked to maintenance, as it facilitates shared responsibility and a realistic assessment of what the school can feasibly manage. A few studies demonstrate examples of adapting constraints into the design like considering lack of maintenance staff in the ambition of the design, opting for woodchips instead of grass, or planting low-maintenance annuals, instead of more time consuming vegetables (Brink and Yost, 2004; Dijk-Wesselius et al., 2022; Ozer, 2007).

Adults often approach schoolyard greening projects with expectations akin to those associated with traditional, ‘tidy’ gardens (Tranter & Malone, 2004). These expectations are not only challenging and time-consuming to meet but also do not align with children’s

perception of a 'tidy' yard. To establish a feasible vision for the yard and the realistic maintenance requirements, it is crucial for the the school community to "adjust their norms for neatness," embracing the inclusion of loose parts and natural, messy elements children crave (Blair, 2009, p. 17; Tranter & Malone, 2004).

Several obstacles impede maintenance efforts, though numerous initiatives have discovered innovative management strategies to sustain greenspaces. Weather conditions, while uncontrollable, impact the use and upkeep of these spaces. Cold, rain, or excessive heat can discourage both children and teachers from engaging with greenspace, rendering maintenance more difficult during substantial portions of the year (Huys et al., 2017). School holidays also create maintenance challenges due to the reduced availability of individuals to perform upkeep tasks (Huys et al., 2017). A common recommendation for schools with gardens is to plant vegetation that flowers or produces fruits and vegetables either in spring or fall by delaying planting or choosing specific varieties (Huys et al., 2017).

Funding represents another major barrier for schools. Typically, funding is allocated for the creation of greenspace with minimal resources earmarked for ongoing maintenance (Dyment & Reid, 2005). This lack of allocated funds poses a significant challenge, as several studies cite the availability of financial resources as a driver of success (DeMarco et al., 1999; Giezen & Pellerey, 2021; Ozer, 2007). One estimate suggests an annual budget of 1500€ to 2000€ annually to maintain one schoolyard, although this figure may have increased since the time of the study (Giezen & Pellerey, 2021).

The time and labor required for maintenance are considerable hurdles, particularly for often overburdened teachers who struggle with upkeep responsibilities (Derr & Rigolon, 2017; Ozer, 2007; Graham et al., 2005). Teachers frequently bear the brunt of the labor required for green schoolyards, and high staff turnover exacerbates the challenge of retraining new personnel (Ozer, 2007; Derr & Rigolon, 2017). Many teachers lack the time, knowledge, or experience necessary for effective maintenance (Blair, 2009). It is essential to stress the importance of establishing support structures for yard maintenance to minimize the burden on schools and ensure that responsibilities are not concentrated among a few motivated teachers, ensuring the longevity of greenspaces (Giezen & Pellerey, 2021; Huys et al., 2017). In some cases, hiring a gardener to assist with the technical aspects of care, if financially feasible, might be beneficial (Blair, 2009). Engaging students, parents, and the broader community can also alleviate some of the burden on teachers and address funding challenges by soliciting donations, technical assistance, or volunteer labor, fostering a strong sense of community around the school (Ozer, 2007).

Student participation in maintenance can take various forms, such as classroom learning, after-school clubs, or recess activities. Schools may differ in their approach, either

mandating formal assistance or allowing students to contribute based on their enthusiasm (Dyment, 2008). Involving students can also serve as a preventative measure, enhancing their understanding of plant care and empathy for maintenance efforts, which may reduce the potential for damages to green elements from children's play (Jansson et al., 2014). . When students participate in maintaining their own yard, they develop a stronger, more positive attachment to the school and are more likely to discuss the garden at home, involving their parents in school activities (Flax et al., 2020).

Parents play a crucial role in supporting the maintenance of the schoolyard, particularly during school holidays. Schools lacking parental assistance often face challenges in upkeep (Derr & Rigolon, 2017; Ozer, 2007; Huys et al., 2017). To encourage parental involvement, it is beneficial to initiate communication before the yard's implementation to mitigate potential conflicts or disagreements (Dijk-Wesselius et al., 2021). A survey by Dijk-Wesselius et al. (2021) indicated that parents preferred participating through representative groups, although nearly half expressed reluctance to assist, citing time constraints, unawareness of the need for help, or lack of expertise as the primary reasons (Dijk-Wesselius et al., 2021). Expanding the scope of maintenance to include the broader community can provide valuable support. For instance, a study of 22 elementary schools in Colorado found that external volunteers were instrumental (Brink & Yost, 2004).

Involving a diverse range of stakeholders is essential for the sustainable management of green schoolyards. These projects can't stand on a singular figurehead, so shared responsibility is key to creating a semi-decentralized structure that encourages ongoing participation and distributes the labor burden (Flax et al., 2020). Some schools establish committees to manage the garden, including representatives from various corners of school life – teachers, students, administrators, parents, community volunteers – to foster a collective sense of responsibility (Hazzard et al., 2011).

The role of cleaning staff is pivotal in maintaining the schoolyard, and their training and willingness to engage is vital for keeping the space in good condition. Unfortunately, poorly trained staff may inadvertently damage native plant gardens or areas intentionally left messy for educational purposes (Children and Nature Network, 2016). Incorporating maintenance staff into the design phase can enhance their understanding of the specific care requirements for the garden, contributing to its long-term success (Children and Nature Network, 2016).

2.5 Pedagogic Use

Utilizing a green schoolyard for pedagogic purposes presents a valuable opportunity to enhance maintenance practices and integrate these spaces into the broader culture and community of a school. Empirical evidence indicates that outdoor classrooms are

infrequently used and tend to replicate the constraints of traditional curriculum practices (Dyment, 2005). Despite their potential, green schoolyards and outdoor classrooms have not yet been fully incorporated into standard educational practices and are often perceived as an “add on” to school programming (Dyment, 2005, p. 40). Science is frequently identified as the predominant subject taught outdoors due to its inherent connection to nature (Graham et al., 2005). Newly renovated schoolyards offer a unique opportunity to create intentional learning environments, fostering a type of “experiential, inquiry-based learning grounded in concrete experience” (Blair, 2009, p. 19).

Learning in the schoolyard occurs through formal channels like outdoor classes, and informal settings, such as unstructured play, which facilitates self-directed exploration (Dyment, 2005). Effectively employing the schoolyard for pedagogical purposes requires altering teachers’ perceptions regarding the potential of outdoor learning and motivating a sense of curiosity to develop relevant curriculum materials (DeMarco et al., 1999). Schools that successfully integrate these practices showcase a range of innovative outdoor activities across various subjects. For instance, one school used a bar graph exercise for students to track plant varieties while weeding, while another class utilized sidewalk chalk for mathematical exercises outdoors (Brink & Yost, 2004). Such methods of learning are designed to engage and motivate, particularly in subjects where they may exhibit less enthusiasm within a traditional classroom setting (Gilchrist, et al., 2017). Overall, structured, outdoor learning offers numerous benefits, accommodating diverse learning styles, promoting physical skills and activity, fostering connections with nature, and enhancing problem-solving and cognitive skills (Maller, 2005).

Outdoor informal learning plays a crucial role, reflecting the general benefits of nature contact for children. Play time in the schoolyard allows children to engage with their environment autonomously, cultivating a deeper connection with nature, sparking curiosity about their surroundings, and building self-confidence (Gilchrist et al., 2017). The quality of outdoor play is strongly influenced by the school’s approach to defining learning and the availability of informal learning opportunities (Tranter & Malone, 2004). Additionally, children’s learning is influenced by their observations of adults’ attitudes towards the environment; the care, enthusiasm, and interest exhibited by adults can significantly enhance children’s engagement with outdoor spaces (Dyment, 2005).

Academic performance is also positively impacted by outdoor learning. Evidence suggests that children learn “more effectively” in environmental based education exhibiting higher standardized test scores and classroom assessments (Ernst & Monroe, 2004, p. 508). This improvement is largely attributed to the heightened engagement and enthusiasm that comes with the freedom, stimulation, and exploration of outdoor learning (Ernst & Monroe, 2004). Outdoor classroom experiences are interdisciplinary and problem-based, providing

hands-on sensory-rich experiences that bring academic subjects to life (Blair, 2009, p. 16; Dymont, 2005).

The enthusiasm generated by nature-based learning can foster an enduring environmental affinity in students. Research indicates that early contact with nature often leads to more environmental stewardship in adulthood (Blair, 2009; Wilson 1997; Waliczek & Zajicek, 1999). Such feelings also grow from participation in outdoor activities that engender responsibility in children, inspiring feelings of “empowerment” and “ownership,” as reported by children (Maller, 2005, p. 19).

In addressing maintenance concerns, integrating outdoor learning activities with student participation in upkeep can be highly beneficial. By engaging in roles such as gardening, students actively “participate in the process of life,” instilling a stronger sense of place by regularly modifying and impacting their environment (Bell & Dymont, 2008; Blair, 2009, p. 19; Dowdell et al., 2011). Parents and teachers express concerns about children returning dirty and wet from contact with the outdoors, but this is precisely what excites children, an eagerness that should be harnessed as a tool (Dymont, 2005). Involving students in daily maintenance not only alleviates the burden on cleaning staff and teachers but also reinforces the myriad benefits of outdoor learning and play.

Despite the considerable benefits, several barriers impede the widespread adoption of outdoor learning. These include teachers’ personal views, institutional curriculum demands, and practical challenges like time constraints, lack of support, insufficient training, and safety concerns (Blair, 2009; Graham et al., 2005; Hazzard et al., 2011; Gilchrist et al., 2017). The ethos surrounding outdoor learning within a school can either facilitate or hinder its integration into the curriculum. Support from school leadership is pivotal in either advancing or obstructing environmental education initiatives (Dymont, 2005; Hazzard et al., 2011; DeMarco et al., 1999). Teacher’s perceptions of outdoor learning as an effective pedagogical strategy are crucial, playing a significant role in motivation (Dymont, 2005).

Teacher’s knowledge, confidence, and experience in outdoor settings significantly influence their willingness to adopt environmental education practices. A lack of expertise in gardening or outdoor teaching often results in insufficient knowledge and confidence to utilize the schoolyard effectively (Dymont, 2005; DeMarco et al., 1999). Without proper training, concerns about losing control of students outdoors and assumptions about traditional pedagogical methods may hinder teachers’ willingness to explore outdoor learning (Dymont, 2005). The perception that teachers must be experts in their subject matter, coupled with limited time for curriculum development, further discourages the adoption of outdoor teaching (Dymont, 2005).

Formal curriculum requirements and educational policies further emphasize traditional academics and standardized testing also constrain the integration of outdoor learning (Dyment & Reid, 2005; Brink & Yost, 2004). For full adoption of an outdoor curriculum, it must be recognized as “a legitimate form of learning and teaching,” integrated into the educational framework (Dyment, 2005).

To mainstream environmental education, teachers must be provided with necessary resources and curriculum materials for outdoor teaching (Dyment, 2005). Effective training and professional development opportunities are critical for equipping teachers with the skills and confidence needed to implement environmental education (Dyment & Reid, 2005; Ernst & Monroe, 2004). Teachers must “recognize and believe that gardening is a valuable teaching tool” and “genuinely understand the value of learning through gardening,” which is facilitated through “opportunities to see gardening used successfully as a teaching tool” (DeMarco et al., 1999). Research indicates that teachers are eager for ongoing training to develop the skills and confidence to partake in outdoor education (Dyment, 2005; Giezen & Pellerey, 2021; Children and Nature Network, 2016).

2.6 Neighborhood Impact

The impact of a green schoolyard can extend far beyond the immediate school community if embraced as a neighborhood-wide asset. Although schools often express concerns about potential vandalism, studies indicate that only a small percent actually experience an increase in crime, with the majority reporting no change or a decrease (Bell & Dyment, 2008). While the research on broader neighborhood impacts of schoolyard greening remains limited, some studies suggest that nurturing a connection between the neighborhood and school through shared greenspace can enhance cooperation and cohesion within communities (Bell & Dyment, 2008; Rooney, 2017). Rather than restricting access in the name of safety, an inclusive approach can extend the sense of belonging that students experience within their school to the wider neighborhood thereby reducing feelings of alienation that may lead to undesirable behaviors (Rooney, 2017).

Open schoolyards provide a space for communities to unite, friendships to grow, and to experience the health benefits of greening (Giezen and Pellerey, 2021). In particular, when neighborhoods are invited to participate in the maintenance of these spaces, the schoolyard can come to “embody the effort, care, and vision of those involved,” cultivating a shared sense of community pride (Bell & Dyment, 2008, p. 83). Local residents with gardening expertise, or simply a desire to learn, can alleviate the school’s maintenance responsibilities while simultaneously reaping the benefits of environmental contact (Gilchrist et al., 2017).

Despite the mutual benefits for both the school and community, opening schoolyards to the public is a complex undertaking that requires careful strategic planning. Many schools opt

for joint-use agreements to establish schedules for opening times, as well as guidelines for activities and conduct in the yard (Chawla, 2015; Children and Nature Network, 2016). In some cases, schools avoid imposing strict rules and prohibitions, instead employing creative strategies to encourage respectful behavior while maintaining a welcoming environment (Flax et al., 2020). Formal partnerships with local organizations and businesses can further facilitate collaborations in maintenance and use, strengthening the schoolyard's role in the community (Children and Nature Network, 2016; Blair, 2009). Programming in the yard can invite community members who may feel hesitant to enter the space to participate and enjoy nature (Derr & Rigolon, 2017).

III. Case Study: Brussels

3.1 Green Schoolyards in Belgium

Looking at Belgium, the two regions of Flanders and Wallonia developed their own schoolyard greening initiatives. In the southern, francophone region of Wallonia, the initiative *Ose le Vert*, was launched in 2016 in partnership with the ASBL (*association sans but lucratif*, non-profit associations in Belgium) GoodPlanet Belgium and Natagora, with the goal of adding a nature corner in primary schools. The project emphasizes conviviality, contact with nature, and biodiversity by creating spaces that facilitate environmental connection through play and pedagogy (Natagora). In addition to constructing these nature corners, *Ose le Vert* supports schools with a coach who provides technical assistance, training, and problem-solving during six site visits along with pedagogical tools to integrate the project into the educational curriculum (Natagora).

Between 2016 and 2023, the project impacted 470 schools, with an additional 90 schools in the upcoming fifth edition (*Ose le Vert*). In the project's most recent round, schools received personalized support through four visits and financial assistance of up to 3,000€, with an additional subsidy available for soil de-pollution for ten urban schools (*Ose le Vert*). The initiative's high demand, evidenced by 1,200 applications for the first four editions, highlights a significant interest in school greening projects (*Ose le Vert*; GoodPlanet). To be selected, schools must prioritize the presence of native plants, stimulate student interaction with nature, foster conviviality and well-being, commit to a collaborative and organized implementation process, integrate the project within the school, and plan for the maintenance and management of the new greenspace (*Ose le Vert*, 2023).

In Flanders, Outdoor Learning and Play, *Buiten Leren en Spelen* (BLES), supported by the Flemish government, The Artevelde University College, and NextGeneration EU, aims to green five urban schoolyards between 2023 and 2026. The initiative will de-pave 16,274m² of surface area by creating play islands, adding trees, flowers, and small meadows at an estimated cost of 328,000€ (Omgeving Vlaanderen). BLES is led by a network of experts and organizations focused on creating climate-adaptive schoolyards through a participatory approach involving students, teachers, and maintenance staff in the design process (Omgeving Vlaanderen). Each school's project is individualized, involving various participatory methods such as post-it mood boards and drawings, written ideas, and classroom discussions (Omgeving Vlaanderen). Additionally, some, if not all, schoolyards will be accessible to local residents and organizations outside school hours (Omgeving Vlaanderen). The project also includes opportunities to engage parents and teachers with experts to share experiences and lessons learned (Omgeving Vlaanderen).

In the Limburg province of Flanders, Provincial Nature Center is greening 60 schools through a subsidized, guided process. The project, funded by subsidies ranging from 5,000€ to 15,000€ per school, assists with vision formation and a participatory design process, guiding future educational use of the yard (Provincial Nature Center). The ongoing initiative invites all primary and secondary schools to apply, as long as their proposed project will “strengthen local biodiversity, promote the well-being of students, and encourage educational use of the playground” (Provincial Nature Center).

3.2 Opération Ré-création

In Brussels, the conversation surrounding schoolyard greening began with the development of the 2021 guide Rethink the Schoolyard, *Repenser la Cour de Récréation*, created in partnership with Brussels Environment and Perspective Brussels. The manual provided clear guidance and tools for schools seeking to improve their yards, but lacked tangible examples to inspire creative initiatives. Out of this gap, along with political support leading to funding from the Minister of the Environment, Opération Ré-création was born.

Opération Ré-création aims to transform hot, impermeable asphalt yards into spaces contributing to the climate transition, with goals to improve water management and soil permeability, reinforce green networks and enhance biodiversity. The project also focuses on providing relaxing, accessible greenspaces for the school community and neighborhood, enhancing the overall learning experience.

Launched in 2021 with a call for proposals, the project is divided into two phases (fig. 1): *Analysis and Definition*, including the technical diagnostic, soil analysis, awareness raising, meeting between the school actors, and discussions about management and assistance with opening and maintenance; and *Design and Validation*, the sketch and pre-project.

Figure 1: Overview of Opération Ré-création’s participative timeline (Source: Bubble.Brussels)

The project sets out a vision for completed yards, highlighting outcomes such as maximizing vegetated surfaces, cooling down temperatures, creating permeable surfaces to manage rainwater, and using greenspaces as outdoor classrooms. While also specifying a series of expectations such as building play structures out of durable and circular materials, ensuring a maximum surface area is vegetated, and a specific maintenance plan is developed implicating the users of the yard.

To reach the project’s goals and vision, Brussels Environment provides accompaniment to the schools in the form of:

- A participative design process leading to a budgeted maintenance plan.
- Analysis of the soil quality, results of which are included in the final design and potential soil remediation actions are taken.
- Assistance with hiring contractors and monitoring construction.
- Financial support of up to €300,000 per yard.
- Support for using the new yard and greenspace in an educational context.
- A maintenance plan that is accessible to each school depending on its resources.
- Support to set up a system for opening up the yard with community partnerships.

The initial timeline for the project (fig. 2) has faced delays due to rising budgetary costs and difficulties in securing construction companies, resulting in only one school beginning construction as of June 2024, and the rest slated to start late 2024 or early 2025.

Figure 2: Original timeline for Opération Ré-création (Source: original image)

Application Process

Schools from all age groups and affiliations were encouraged to apply, provided they met environmental regulations and demonstrated a commitment to the project's goals. The application criteria required compliance with environmental regulations, stipulating that schools must be situated in areas deficient in greenspace, and located in a zone designated priority by the *Plan Regional*, and/or in a zone contributing to the heat island in the Brussels Capital Regional, as outlined in official maps (fig. 3 & 4). The school's location within these specific catchment areas was a prerequisite for eligibility, with schools encouraged to meet the maximum of the following criteria:

- ❖ Building's energy efficiency;
- ❖ Capacity of rainwater reduction;
- ❖ Soil conditions;
- ❖ Accessibility of the yard to the neighborhood;
- ❖ Coordination between the school and the organizing authority;
- ❖ Motivation to open the yard outside school hours; and
- ❖ Resources available to the school to maintain the project.

Figure 3: Brussels Environment map of areas lacking greenspaces accessible to the public (Source: Bubble.Brussels)

Figure 4: Opération Ré-creation schools on map of heat stress in Brussels (Source: Bubble.Brussels)

The call for proposal urged schools to refer to the guide “Repenser sa Cour” to conduct an initial assessment of the yard, identify needs and priorities, and articulate their level of ambition and willingness to open the yard. Additionally, schools were expected to provide detailed plans of the existing yard, participate in preparatory meetings, identify representatives for meetings, integrate the process into their work schedule, engage the entire school community, and develop innovative, realistic designs that could be replicated by other schools.

The call for proposals yielded 62 applications, of which 20 were selected by an advisory committee comprising representatives from the Fédération Wallonie-Bruxelles, Perspective.brussels, VGC, Tournesol-Zonnebloem asbl, Écorce sa, Réseau Idée asbl, NME-Brussel, and Bruxelles Environnement. One school withdrew due to upcoming construction work that rendered them ineligible, leaving a final total of 19 participating schools.

Stakeholders

A diverse group of stakeholders, as outlined in figures 5 and 6, play a crucial role in the multifaceted approach of Opération Ré-creation. This group includes the association Tournesol-Zonnebloem, which manages the initial participatory process; two consortiums of architects collaborating with ecologists; and 21 Solutions, a firm contributing to the participatory process and development of community partnerships.

Stakeholder	Role
Brussels Environment	Project funder and leader, additional support from the Minister of the Environment and Perspective Brussels.
21 Solutions	A firm supporting organizations in climate transitions. Part of the design team managing the participatory process with adult actors, in addition to supporting community engagement efforts.
Tournesol-Zonnenbloem	Environmental education association: Leading the participatory process and providing training on outdoor learning and maintenance.
ÁRTER	Consortium 1: Architectural firm in charge of projects.
Écorce	Consortium 1: Engineering and consulting firm. Conducting ecological assessment and supporting maintenance.
AAC	Consortium 2: Architectural firm in charge of projects.
OSMOS	Consortium 2: Design and development agency, working on co-creation and public partnerships.

Figure 5: Description of stakeholders (Source: original image)

Figure 6: Map of Stakeholders in Opération Ré-création (Source: original image)

While most of the actors mentioned above continue their work on Opération Ré-création, OSMOS, partnered with the architecture firm AAC, is no longer involved in the project. This decision stems from a misalignment in goals, expectations, and processes, which have remained unclear.

Participatory Process

Figure 7: Timeline of participatory design process (Source Bubble.Brussels)

A participatory approach, outlined in figure 7, is fundamental to Opération Ré-création, aiming to transform environmental habits and practices of students, teachers, parents, and maintenance staff. To ensure the schoolyard transformation aligns with the needs of all stakeholders and is sustainable in the long term, engagement from the entire school community is essential.

Construction

Following the participatory design phase and finalization of plans, schools, with the assistance of the architectural consortia and Brussels Environment, are required to draft planning permission applications (where necessary), launch the call for public works contract, commence construction, and oversee the building of the new yard (Bubble Brussels-B). A distinctive aspect of this project is that schools receive direct subsidies from Brussels Environment to finance construction works. However, the schools themselves (or their organizing authorities) are responsible for managing most of the construction phase, including the selection of an enterprise and monitoring progress.

The construction budget varies by school but is capped at 300,000€. This budget is allocated for works related to greening the yard and for their use as an educational and recreational space both during and after school hours (Brussels Environment, 2021). The subsidy does not cover costs related to non-greening improvements, maintenance, or project coordination (Brussels Environment, 2021). Additionally, soil analysis falls under the charge of Brussels Environment and is not included in the subsidy. The funding is disbursed to schools in stages: 30% upon notification of eligibility, 20% upon publication of the public work contract, 30% at the beginning of construction, and the remaining 20% at provisional completion (Brussels Environment, 2021).

The 19 public tenders were launched via an e-procurement platform by the schools Organizing Authorities. Key criteria for awarding the contract includes price, planning and operational suitability within the school environment. While Brussels Environment does not directly award the contracts, they provide support by recommending criteria, such as promoting the circular economy, although schools are not obligated to adopt these recommendations.

The original call for proposals specified that students and teachers would be invited to participate in the construction of educational features such as ponds, gardens, aromatic spirals, compost areas, fruit tree planting, or shelter construction (Brussels Environment, 2021).

Maintenance, Pedagogic Use, and Neighborhood Impact

As part of the process, Brussels Environment assists schools in developing maintenance plans by helping to identify internal and external partnerships to ensure the school's autonomy in maintenance efforts. Similarly, Brussels Environment offers optional support for schools to utilize their yards for pedagogical purposes and conduct outdoor classes.

Opening the schoolyard to the community is a mandated requirement, although the specific manner of implementation is intentionally vague. Partnerships could include sharing the space with local community groups who assist with maintenance over vacations, providing access to students and parents on weekends, or renting the yard to non-profit organizations for various activities. Brussels Environment supports schools in brainstorming and implementing such partnerships, encouraging maximal community engagement.

3.3 Education Structure in Brussels

The Brussels educational system reflects Belgium's complex linguistic and cultural landscape. Schools are divided by language communities, either belonging to the French or Flemish network, and then subdivided in schools belonging to the municipalities or associations (i.e. religious institutions). Behind each school is also a *pouvoir organisateur* (PO), the organizing authority, akin to the schools 'employer' who assists with administrative and curriculum needs. An outline of the various educational categories is summarized in figure 8.

Educational Stages	Pre-primary education <i>Kleuteronderwijs or Maternelle</i>	Children aged 2.5 to 6 years.
	Primary education <i>Lager Onderwijs or Primaire</i>	Ages 6 to 12 years, collectively referred to as a <i>l'école fondamentale</i> when paired with pre-primary education.
	Secondary education <i>Secundair Onderwijs or Secondaire</i>	Students aged 12 to 18 years.
Linguistic Distinctions Each language group adheres to different curriculums, educational standards, school holidays, and safety regulations.	Dutch-language schools	<i>Gemeenschapscholens</i> or 'Community Schools,' representing the Flemish community.
	French-language schools	<i>Écoles Officielles</i> or 'Official Schools', affiliated with the Walloon community.
Pouvoir Organisateur (PO), or 'organizing authority.' The PO is the authority, person, or legal entity that assumes responsibility for the school, determining the educational approach, curriculum, staffing decisions, and the overarching values of the institution. Some POs manage a single school, while others oversee multiple.	L'enseignement officiel	Schools managed by public authorities, like one of Brussels nineteen municipalities within Brussels.
	L'enseignement libre	Schools managed by non-public authorities, including associations or religious institutions.

Figure 8: Breakdown of the educational framework in Brussels (Source: original image)

3.4 Overview of Case Study Schools

Having established an understanding of the Brussels school system's complexity, we will examine four of the nineteen schools participating in Opération Ré-création. These schools represent diverse contexts across Brussels, and have been selected to illustrate OR among the varying socio-economic, racial, and immigration background present in the city. Below is an overview of existing program and neighborhood profiles, summarized in the tables in figures 9-12 and maps in figures 13-16, noting that neighborhood data often provides a more accurate picture of conditions.

School A

School A located in the municipality of Etterbeek and neighborhood of Saint-Pierre, serves 340 students in pre-primary and primary education and operates under *l'enseignement officiel*, with the Municipality of Etterbeek as its organizing authority. The school benefits from an active parents' association that collaborates to support students, helping newly arrived families integrate, organizing activities, and disseminating information.

The neighborhood of Saint-Pierre is characterized by a relatively affluent demographic, higher average income, and lower unemployment rates compared to the broader region. Although the area has a higher population density than the regional median, it remains the least dense among the case study neighborhoods. There is a relatively high percentage of newly arrived residents to the region, although this data is a bit murky because there is no information on the origin of the new arrivals. Saint-Pierre also shows significant proximity to public greenspaces, although it has a higher percentage of impermeable surfaces and lower vegetation compared to regional averages. Air pollution levels in the area are generally consistent with the regional average, making it one of the less polluted neighborhoods in the case study.

School B

School B hosts 290 students, and is a primary, catholic, school within the *réseau libre catholique*, with a religious asbl as the organizing authority. The school has an active parents' association that collaborates with the director and teachers on new initiatives and school improvements.

Noteworthy environmentally-focused projects initiated by the school, preceding Opération Ré-création, include the *Projet Potager*, launched by two teachers and aimed at teaching students to pay more attention to nature through participation in a vegetable garden, alongside *Projet Zero Dechet* to raise awareness about waste, learning to sort trash and reduce waste.

The school is also engaged in local partnerships, like with the local municipality to measure

air pollution and understand their role in improving air quality. Other partnerships include a local association who manages the day care, supervision during lunch time, summer camp, along with hosting afterschool activities.

Located in the neighborhood of Flagey Malibran in the municipality of Ixelles, this area has income levels aligned with the regional average, though it experiences higher unemployment rates and significant population density and percentage of new residents. Similar to School A, there is also a higher than average percent of students in the neighborhood attending school near their home. The neighborhood enjoys high access to public greenspace, but faces challenges considering the high percentage of impermeable surfaces and low vegetation rates.. The air in Flagey Malibran is poorer compared to other parts of the Brussels Capital Region, particularly concerning NO2 levels.

School C

School C accommodates 241 students in pre-primary and primary education, is part of *l'enseignement officiel*, with the municipality of Jette serving as the organizing authority.

The municipality of Jette exhibits slightly higher average income and slightly lower unemployment rates relative to the broader region, The neighborhood of Woeste, where the school is situated, shows a lower income level and higher population density compared to the regional median. Both the municipality and neighborhood have limited access to public greenspace compared to the region, and the neighborhood has the lowest access in comparison to the other schools. The neighborhood also has a high rate of impermeable surfaces and low rate of vegetation. Neighborhood air pollution is also relatively high.

School D

School D is a comprehensive school serving pre-primary, primary, and secondary education with a total of 900 students. It is part of *l'enseignement officiel*, with Wallonie-Bruxelles Enseignement as its organizing authority. The secondary education curriculum offers a general education track, in addition to technical and professional training.

The school is notable for its Garden of Delights, *Jardin des Délices*, an ambitious gardening project created in 2020 by two teachers. The garden is open to the entire school community to enjoy, work in, or use as a learning space. The garden includes various elements such as garden beds, composts, vegetable gardens, ornamental and aromatic plants, supporting a broad range of interdisciplinary educational objectives in French, science, math, languages, and cooking. Additionally, the garden functions as a meeting place to encourage collaboration and relationship building between the students, while promoting environmental stewardship through educational engagement. The garden has garnered attention, including a visit from Princess Claire and the Minister of Education in April 2023.

Located in Laeken, within the municipality of Brussels (distinct from the Brussels Capital Region), and specifically in the Vieux Laeken Est neighborhood, School D is situated in an area characterized by socio-economic challenges. This neighborhood reports the lowest average income and highest unemployment rates among the four school areas. It also exhibits the lowest percentage of new residents compared to the other school neighborhoods, and a population density comparable to the neighborhood around Clarté. The neighborhood has the lowest access to greenspace and most significant air and noise pollution of the four.

School	Location	Median Revenue After Tax (2021)	Percent Unemployment (2021)	Population Density (hab/km ²) (2023)	Percent of New Residents to the Territory (2014)
Regional Median		16,930€	17.78%	7641.66	
School A	Municipality: Etterbeek	18,170.85€	14.74%	15.612,41	
	Neighborhood: Saint-Pierre	18,859.92€	12.52%	18.028,18	54.68%
School B	Municipality: Ixelles	18,213.31€	16.4%	13.807,07	
	Neighborhood: Flagey Malibran	16,875.16€	19.65%	20.901,12	53.64%
School C	Municipality: Jette	17,743.39€	16.2%	10.348,77	
	Neighborhood: Woeste	16,477€	17.22%	18.929,21	42.39%
School D	Municipality: Bruxelles	15,632.18€	19.72%	5.872,14	
	Neighborhood: Vieux Laeken Est	13,798.04€	22.6	18.861,42	41.1%

Figure 9: Neighborhood Demographics (Source: Monitoring les Quartiers)

School	Neighborhood	Percent neighborhood children attending kindergarten near their home	Percent neighborhood children attending elementary school near their home	Percent neighborhood children attending secondary school near their home
Regional Median		72.11%	66.40%	35.99%
School A	Saint-Pierre	85.11%	81.9%	49.58%
School B	Flagey Malibrans	78.65%	74.03%	46.85%
School C	Woeste	72.33%	68.06%	47.27%
School D	Vieux Laeken Est	73.9%	72.6%	51.31%

Figure 10: Neighborhood Education Statistics (2022-2023) (Source: Monitoring les Quartiers)

School	Neighborhood	Avg. annual concentration of NO ₂ (µg / m ³) (2022)	Avg. annual concentration of PM _{2.5} particulates (2.5µm (PM _{2.5}) (µg / m ³)) (2022)	Noise Levels (multi-exposition) Lden (24h) (dB (A)) (2016)
Regional Median		16.85	9.75	57,67
School A	Saint-Pierre	16,7	10	51,12
School B	Flagey Malibrans	19,6	10,2	53,11
School C	Woeste	18,8	10,5	55,69
School D	Vieux Laeken Est	20,2	10,6	59,19

Figure 11: Neighborhood Noise and Air Pollution Data (Source: Monitoring les Quartiers)

School	Location	Percent Vegetated (2020)	Percent Impermeable Surfaces (2022)	Percent Population in Proximity to Public Green Space
Regional Median		52,4%	53.2%	81,75%
School A	Municipality: Etterbeek	27%	84,22%	92,19%
	Neighborhood: Saint-Pierre	23%	87,01%	99,13%
School B	Municipality: Ixelles	32%	76,31%	90,82%
	Neighborhood: Flagey Malibran	21%	89,39%	90,67%
School C	Municipality: Jette	52%	56,29%	77,34%
	Neighborhood: Woeste	29%	86,48%	67,5%
School D	Municipality: Bruxelles	40%	62,89%	77,17%
	Neighborhood: Vieux Laeken Est	23%	87,63%	69,83%

Figure 12: Neighborhood Greening Statistics (Source: Monitoring les Quartiers)

Figure 13: Map of the Percent Vegetation Cover of Brussels Territory (2020)

Figure 14: Map of Percent Population in Proximity to Public Greenspace in Brussels (2021)

Figure 15: Map of Avg. annual concentration of PM2.5 particulates in Brussels (2.5µm (PM2.5) (µg / m³)) (2022)

Figure 16: Percent Impermeable Surfaces in Brussels (2022)

IV. Methodology

To address the research questions, the study was divided into two main categories, 1) a retrospective analysis of the project to date, grounded in the experiences of interviewees and immersive participation; and 2) a forward looking investigation into the project's future, utilizing interview data supported by an extensive literature review.

The research employed three primary methodologies: 1) semi-structured interviews; 2) immersive participation; and 3) a literature review. Four out of the nineteen schools in Opération Ré-création were selected as case studies due to their geographic diversity, representing various contexts within Brussels. Schools A, B, and C of these schools participated in workshops hosted by 21 Solutions to discuss maintenance and opening of the yard, which I observed, facilitating opportunities for first hand contact and to personally engage in discussions. The School D school was chosen for its long-standing teaching garden, serving as a valuable comparative study to Opération Ré-création.

4.1 Interviews

Interviews were conducted within the framework of the CoolSchools project, a European project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation project, the Spanish Research Agency (AEI), Innoviris (Brussels Capital Region), Dutch Research Council (NWO), The Research Foundation-Flanders (FWO), and Agence Nationale de la Recherche (ANR). The project aims to analyze the co-benefits of nature-based solutions in schools, to understand how greening interventions catalyze urban transformations. Studying schools in Barcelona, Rotterdam, Paris, and Brussels, CoolSchools explores schoolyard greening across a spectrum of approaches, including health, access and equity, biodiversity, inclusive governance, safety, and education. Brussels and Opération Ré-création serve as the 'Urban Living Lab,' for testing participatory co-creation methods.

As part of CoolSchools, interviews were conducted with participants in Opération Ré-création and other stakeholders, following an interview framework developed by CoolSchools, and administered by the research company Ipsos. Some interviews were conducted by representatives from Brussels Environment or CoolSchools researchers using the same framework.

I conducted my interviews within the context of CoolSchools, aligning with complementary research goals and shared interviewees. Semi-structured interviews were held in April and May 2024, both in person and virtually, in either English or French according to the interviewee's preference. The interview questions were developed using a framework guided by the research questions, focusing on reflections of the project to date, followed by questions about future scenarios for the yard. The aim was to obtain a comprehensive

overview of Opération Ré-création, encompassing a diverse array of participant perspectives.

Between the 18 interviews done by Ipsos and 19 by myself, a total of 37 interviews were conducted with 27 individuals and three student groups, with one response written via email (fig. 17). Of the nine stakeholders directly implicated in Opération Ré-création, three work for Brussels Environment, and the rest from companies and nonprofits subcontracted by Brussels Environment. An additional three interviews with external stakeholders from organizations working on schoolyard greening, and a capital city's municipality. Among the schools, eight teachers, four directors, two parents, and an after school coordinator were interviewed, along with groups of 3-6 children from schools B, C, and D. Interviewees skewed more towards women, with 10 male interviewees and 17 women. The student groups were a mix of boys and girls, with boys slightly more represented. All 37 interviews were transcribed and coded following a framework guided by the research questions.

Interview guides were tailored for three groups, 1) schools, 2) Opération Ré-création stakeholders, and 3) external stakeholders. For all three groups, interviews began by asking interviewees to articulate their understanding of the overall goal of Opération Ré-création. This consistent inquiry aimed to determine if a centralized and unified vision of the project existed, which is pertinent to various research concerns, including participatory design, maintenance plans, public accessibility, and curriculum integration. Generally, questions asked interviewees to recount their experiences with greening schoolyards, reflecting on lessons learned throughout the process.

Questions for the schools focused on the participatory process, project presentation, initial expectations, and general feedback on the project. They aimed to investigate how school members felt about the participatory process, and gauge what changes they would make to the project. Questions also explored potential for the future yard, including public access and pedagogical uses, aiming to identify obstacles and solutions.

Interviews with Brussels Environment, architects, and environmental groups directly involved in Opération Ré-création sought to understand the details and intention behind the processes. Questions probed at how the different actors were involved, why each one was responsible for certain tasks (i.e. the schools managing their own call for construction companies), and a reflection on what aspects could be modified and potentially improved during future iterations of the project. Stakeholders were also asked to anticipate future challenges related to curriculum integration and public access, and to propose strategies for overcoming these hurdles.

Interviewing external stakeholders – individuals working for schoolyard and urban greening initiatives, and an urban municipality outside of Brussels – aimed to contextualize Opération Ré-création among other initiatives within Brussels and in other cities. Gaining an outside perspective helped to see OR from a different vantage point, adding voices to the conversation and illuminating new strategies and visions that haven't yet been considered within the frame of OR. Questions focused on experiences with schoolyard greening, changes in student behavior post-greening, public access, and maintenance best practices.

Interviews with children centered around asking them to recount their experience, particularly during the co-creation process, aiming to understand the way children perceived their own involvement. They were also asked to describe the current yard, cataloging what they prefer and wanted to change. Lastly, a plan of the future yard was presented to the kids who pointed to different components they preferred or even recognized as their own suggestion. These interviews were the sole opportunity to hear directly from the children, and provided invaluable insight into their views.

Interviewees were selected based on their involvement in the project, ensuring individuals implicated in the decision making and implementation of Opération Ré-création were included. Within the schools, directors facilitated this process by providing contact information and recommending potential interviewees. The responsiveness of schools varied, posing some challenges in scheduling time to interview members of the school communities. Despite these difficulties, a substantial number of teachers participated, along with a few parents, students, and school staff.

Some participants were interviewed in two stages, once by the CoolSchools project and a second time by myself, providing opportunity for follow up, obtaining additional, more in depth details on issues not previously raised. It was also conceivable that interviews through Ipsos and CoolSchools, at times initiated by Brussels Environment (the project leader and funder), might lead school interviewees to be less candid. To mitigate this, I started each interview by emphasizing the independence of my research from Brussels Environment and any other actors directly involved in Opération Ré-création, assuring interviewees of the anonymity of their responses. This approach aimed to foster a greater sense of security and neutrality among interviewees.

Interviewer	Interviewee Code	Organization / School & Role	Interview Language
KA	BE1	Brussels Environment, Project Leader	French
CoolSchools			English
KA	BE2	Brussels Environment, Project Leader	French
CoolSchools			English
CoolSchools	BE3	Brussels Environment, Department Head	French
KA		ÁRTER, Architects	French
KA		OSMOS	English
KA		Tournesol-Zonnebloem, Participation Coordinator	French
CoolSchools			
KA		21 Solutions, Project Organizer	French
KA		IPSOS, Market Research Company	French
KA		Ian Mostert, IVN Network	English
KA		Laetitia Cloostermans, Less Beton	French
KA		Paris Municipality	French (written response)
KA	T1A	Teacher, School A	French
CoolSchools	DB	Director, School B	French
KA	T1B	Teacher, School B	French
CoolSchools			
KA	T2B	Teacher, School B	French
KA	T3B	Teacher, School B	French
CoolSchools	T4B	Teacher, School B	French
KA	T5B	Afterschool Coordinator, School B	French
CoolSchools	P1B	Parent, School B	French
CoolSchools	P2B	Parent, School B	French
CoolSchools	SB	Student Group, School B (3 students: 4th & 5th grades)	French
CoolSchools	DC	Director, School C	French
KA	T1C	Teacher, School C	French
CoolSchools			
KA	T2C	Teacher, School C	French
CoolSchools			
CoolSchools	SC	Student Group, School C (6 students: 4th, 5th, & 6th grades)	French
CoolSchools	D1D	Director, School D	French
CoolSchools	D2D	Director, School C	French
KA	T1D	Teacher, School D	French
CoolSchools			
KA	SD1	Student Group, School D	French
CoolSchools	SD2	Student Group, School D (6 students: 3rd, 5th, & 6th grades)	French

Figure 17: Table of interviewees (Source: original image)

4.2 Immersive Participation

Immersive participatory research was conducted through a series of workshops with 21 Solutions in the schools, a collective open day with Brussels Environment and all 19 participating schools, and school tours. Notes and reflections from these events provide firsthand accounts and interpretations of Opération Ré-création, enriching the data from interviews. Being present in the schools, among the teachers and students, allowed me to personally experience the unique nuances within each school.

During these workshops, I focused on specific concerns raised by each school, the dynamics between school staff, and how they responded to questions and scenarios presented about future considerations. Schools are their own distinct ecosystems, and without such first hand experience it would be impossible and potentially unethical to draw any conclusions. As a researcher, it was critical to be a participant, to take part in the conversations, and understand the very environment this research is seeking to impact.

4.3 Literature Review

The literature review supported information gathered from interviews and immersive participatory experiences, informing interview questions and providing contextual background. This review also included primary documents from Brussels Environment, 21 Solutions, and Tournesol-Zonnenbloem which offered insights into the selection of schools, the participatory process, and modifications to future iterations of the project.

4.4 Limitations

Several limitations were encountered during the research process. The delay in Opération Ré-création's construction timeline meant that interviews focused more on speculative questions rather than direct experiences and observations of the transformations. To address this, the research questions were adjusted to emphasize two stages, reflection and projection, with a stronger focus on suppositional questions.

Reaching interviewees from schools proved challenging, with many requests for interviews going unanswered or requiring persistent follow up. Interviews with teachers were brief due to their busy schedules, limiting the depth of inquiry. There was a noticeable bias among interviewees, many of whom were actively involved in their school's sustainability efforts and often part of the team leading Opération Ré-création in their respective schools. The bias presents a challenge in gauging broader school community support, as the views of more skeptical participants were underrepresented.

Another significant gap was the limited input from the primary users, the children. Despite conducting some group interviews with students, their perspectives remain underrepresented.

4.5 Positionality and Ethics

Complete neutrality in this research is unattainable, as observational and participatory methods inherently carry biases. To mitigate this, field notes were kept factual and separate from reflective opinions. Interview questions were standardized within each interviewee category to ensure consistency.

As a researcher, I acknowledge the limitations in fully understanding the realities of the milieu studied. Not being a teacher, not having attended school in Belgium, and the temporal distance from my own schooling impact my research perspective. However, I strive to honor the experiences of teachers and students, keeping their realities central to this study.

4.6 Replicability

Belgium's unique cultural context, marked by the complex, and often contentious, linguistic and territorial disputes, makes Opération Ré-création distinct to Brussels. The project's organization reflects the intricate governmental structures of the region. Consequently, the aim of this research is not to generate universally applicable findings but to provide a detailed review and analysis of the Brussels context.

V. Results

5.1 Context Surrounding Opération Ré-création

Drawing on publicly available information regarding Opération Ré-création, coupled with interviews revealed the unique conditions faced by each school, providing greater insight into the application and selection process, as well as budgetary considerations, while further contextualizing the project within the broader movement toward greening schoolyards.

Examining the institutional context, Opération Ré-création was conceived as part of the Brussels Capital Region's efforts to build awareness about the significance of greening urban spaces. At the regional level, various policies lay the groundwork for environmental initiatives, such as school gardens under the Good Food program, de-pollution efforts in collaboration with the Good Soil strategy, the Climate Plan, and Quiet Brussels. Broader policy initiatives, such as the regional Plan Nature (2017), advocate for the greening of schoolyards, contributing to the normalization of nature in educational settings. According to Tournesol-Zonnebloem, schools are increasingly expressing a desire "to be greened" and are actively seeking programs large and small. This demand is partly driven by outdoor learning initiatives that gained popularity during the pandemic.

Opération Ré-création emerged from a critical perspective of the Ose le Vert project in Wallonia, which Brussels was obligated to finance. The critique centered on the project's perceived inadequacies in effectively addressing schoolyard greening, particularly in terms of providing technical assistance. In response, Brussels Environment proposed a new project, Opération Ré-création, to the Ministry of Environment, which was then under the leadership of a Green Party member. The proposal was then incorporated into the Plan Nature with a budget allocation of five million euros. The project, led by the Nature and Education Departments at Brussels Environment, aims to "make [green schoolyards] the norm" (BE1), while also striving to "bridge the gap" between disparities in access to greenspace (BE3). The initiative involves a number of stakeholders, beginning with Brussels Environment and Perspective Brussels, with experts from the water, soil, nature and education department at BE, and alongside schools, architectural consortia, and associations.

The project advanced rapidly, with the call for proposals launching only seven months after securing funding from the Minister of the Environment. Tournesol-Zonnenbloem was first to join the project, focusing on the design process to compensate for the lengthy exercise of selecting architects. In retrospect, a project leader from Brussels Environment acknowledged that "ideally, [the architects] should've been here from the start" (BE1).

5.2 Application & Selection Process

The application process was partially developed in response to the complexities of school management in Brussels. Both the municipalities and Region lack direct control over schools, including municipal schools. As noted by representatives from ÁRTER and Brussels Environment, Opération Ré-création was designed to be voluntary, as municipalities do not possess the authority to mandate such renovations in schools. In contrast with the Oasis project in Paris, where greening initiatives are, at least in part, imposed on the schools because municipalities are essentially renovating their own property. In Brussels, however, Brussels Environment does not exert the same control over educational institutions.

The call for proposals was disseminated via mail to all schools within the Bubble Brussels network, as well as to the school's organizing authority. Brussels Environment received 62 applications, a bit less than anticipated, with a few failing to meet the minimum eligibility criteria. Interviewees who served on the selection jury indicated that their decision-making process evaluated not only the previously outlined environmental criteria, but also the level of support for the project within the school community, the willingness of schools to open their yard to the public, and the overall ambition of the proposals. Additionally, the jury aimed to select a diverse array of schools, representing both language communities and various educational philosophies. There was a shared understanding within Brussels Environment that, "when environmental projects are launched, the first to respond are more often the schools that cater for the most privileged sections of the population" (BE3). As a result, the jury took into account the socio-economic index of the schools, despite this not being an explicit criteria.

5.3 Budget

Brussels Environment provides subsidies of around 300,000€ per school, increased from the original 220,000€. However, schools with more ambitious plans, particularly those involving elements outside the project's original scope, were encouraged to independently secure funding. Approximately eight of the nineteen participating schools had their organizing authorities contribute additional funds ranging from 5,000€ to 30,000€. In hindsight, Brussels Environment acknowledged that the budget should have been set closer to 350,000€ due to the unexpected inflationary pressures.

The funding provided by Brussels Environment covers the subsidy for construction costs, soil decontamination, architectural services, and guidance from associations to facilitate community partnerships, maintenance, and pedagogical use of the yard. However, the budget does not cover ongoing maintenance costs, aside from a few training sessions provided to the schools.

5.4 Overview of Schools

Each school presented a unique context, further illuminated through interviews and site visits. Variations included differences in the source of motivation for participating in Opération Ré-création, concerns with their current yard, and priorities for renovations. Figures 18 through 21 provide an overview of these varying contexts and detail the desired and anticipated transformations.

School A	
Project Origin	Project originated as a request from the parents, and led in large part by the Parent's Association.
Concerns with Existing Yard	Hot, hard floors, and not stimulating for the students.
Requested Interventions	Students: labyrinth, swings, water elements, sport zone, willow hut. Adults: préau reused as an upper terrace with skylight, accessible garden for everyone, fountain and water elements, storage, multifunctional space.
Planned Interventions	4 Zones: calm zone, active zone with no ballgames, active zone with ballgames, transitional welcome zone. The yard includes a labyrinth in the paving, benches, garden, storage, willow hut, sport zone, climbing plants, greened préau, green walls, swings, and water circuit.

Figure 18: Overview of School A and mock-up of planned transformation (Source: Bubble.Brussels)

School B	
Project Origin	Project led by the Director.
Concerns with Existing Yard	The ground is hard and slippery leading to falls, not enough color or greenery, ball games take over the space, garden is too small, puddles, too hot, and nothing to do when it rains.
Requested Interventions	<u>Students:</u> animals, sport zone, bushes to hide in. <u>Adults:</u> space with cabins, climbing plants, space with wood trunks and stumps.
Planned Interventions	4 Zones: calm zone, active zone with no ballgames, active zone with ballgames, transitional welcome zone. The yard includes cabins, a climbing wall, multi-sport area, garden, climbing tree, mural, bike parking, climbing plants, and outdoor classroom space.

Figure 19: Overview of School B and mock-up of planned transformation (Source: Bubble.Brussels).

School C	
Project Origin	Project led by school Director and Municipality.
Concerns with Existing Yard	Play area is too small, the ground is hard and broken leading to falls, garden isn't maintained and not in a good location, disputes between students, children are bored, ball games take up too much space, too hot, and puddles.
Requested Interventions	<p><u>Students:</u> animals, treehouse, and labyrinth.</p> <p><u>Adults:</u> wood games, elevated cabin, multisport space, willow arches to separate zones, huts in the shade.</p>
Planned Interventions	<p>4 Zones: calm zone, active zone with no ballgames, active zone with ballgames, transitional welcome zone.</p> <p>The yard includes climbing plants, amphitheater, cabin on stilts, garden beds, fountain, labyrinth in the paving, climbing tree, and bike parking.</p>

Figure 20: Overview of School C and mock-up of planned transformation (Source: Bubble.Brussels)

School D

Project Origin	Project led by school Directors and teacher in charge of existing garden.
Concerns with Existing Yard	The ground is hard and uneven leading to painful falls, no where to play when it rains, and too hot.

Requested Interventions	<p><u>Primary Students:</u> bikes and scooters, drinking fountain, calm corner.</p> <p><u>Secondary Students:</u> sports zone, calm corner, swings.</p> <p><u>Adults:</u> calm corner with plants, swings for the students, green roof for preexisting préau.</p>
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Planned Interventions	The yard will include calm zones, bike parking, benches, colorful paintings, storage, garden, huts and bushes for hiding, sport zone for secondary students, pond, stream, area with exotic plants, balancing games, climbing wall, greened préau, climbing plants, slide, and walnut tree.
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Figure 21: Overview of School D and mock-up of planned transformation (Source: Bubble.Brussels)

5.5 Communication and Expectations

In addressing the first research question – *How were expectations set and responsibilities communicated between the school and other partners during the co-creation process?* – interview questions explored the motivations and goals behind applying for Opération Ré-création, the establishment of expectations at the project's outset, and the nature of communication within schools and between the various actors involved.

When asked about their primary motivation for participating in Opération Ré-création and the overarching goals of the project, responses from school representatives consistently emphasized the enhancement of greenspace and beautification of the schoolyard. A significant number of respondents also highlighted benefits to student well-being, with one teacher characterizing the project's goal as “restructuring and re-vegetation...so that [the yard] becomes a pleasant play area for children” (T3B). Additional motivations included reducing conflicts and accidents, lowering temperatures, and improving environmental education and awareness.

In some schools, teachers and directors noted that their students predominantly live in apartments with limited access to nature, positioning the redesigned yard as a novel opportunity for students to interact with the environment. The wellbeing aspect appears key, with school players underscoring the educational advantages for students. The director of School C remarked, “The fact that they're in a green area means they'll be able to flourish fully, and I think it's a real educational asset for the teachers too.” A director at School D explicitly stated, “Well-being and environmental education are the two driving forces behind this project” (D1D).

A few participants cited financial incentives, noting that without the project their schools would lack the resources to undertake such extensive renovations. Two interviewees from School D, pointed to improvements to the overall climate as motivation, although notably both come from a school where a substantial garden is already in place. The two parents interviewed, primarily expressed motivations related to their children's physical well-being, including concerns about heat stress, the dangers posed by broken and cracked concrete, and the presence of puddles leading to students returning home wet.

In contrast, Brussels Environment promoted Opération Ré-création as a project rooted in ecology and environmental benefits. A representative from Brussels Environment (BE3) listed four main goals for the project: 1) lower temperatures, 2) improved ground permeability, 3) reinforced ecological systems, and 4) awareness raised through education. For some at Brussels Environment, “the overall objective is to green up school grounds. The

main objective is to bring a crust of green,” while others place equal importance on the educational and social justice component alongside ecological benefits (BE2).

The overarching intention for Brussels Environment was to demonstrate feasibility through tangible examples, aiming to create “big, exemplary projects” as noted by a BE project leader (BE1). After observing the limitations of smaller initiatives such as Ose le Vert, the goal was to prove that larger projects could succeed and merit investment. The project leader summarized this approach:

“At the outset, it was to show that if you had a big enough budget, you could create really large-scale nature features and that they could work. And that, in fact, once money was no longer a constraint, we could...if we accompanied the schools and really helped them through all the stages, show that it actually worked in Brussels too.” (BE1)

Despite the initial intention to create model schoolyards regardless of budget, financial limitations ultimately posed greater challenges than anticipated. This required a careful balance between ambition and practicality, ensuring that the projects remained exemplary without exceeding budget limits. As one representative from Brussels Environment noted “We had to be very careful about the level of ambition...so that we don't end up with micro-projects” (BE3). The architects also highlighted that because of the expansive scope and considerable budget:

“We could do a lot more than greening and making the ground permeable. And so, we really wanted to touch on everything, we're doing the schoolyard, and not just the vegetated or permeable school playground, but the exemplary 21st century school playground, and we're dealing with all the themes, including gender mainstreaming and lots of other things, because we've got a big budget.”

The architects, subcontracted by Brussels Environment, aligned with the project's ecological and environmental objectives, viewing Opération Ré-création as an initiative to redevelop schoolyards, “rethinking existing layouts...with two main objectives: to make schoolyards less waterlogged and to plant them with vegetation, but also to think about the whole educational aspect and the use of schoolyards, and to review how we can offer the best cost-effective solutions.” The architects emphasized the importance of engaging with schools to understand their needs, a process that revealed additional priorities beyond the initial scope. As one architect reflected:

“I think that BE's basic idea was to work only on green and blue. And as soon as we started working with schools, we were told that green and blue were fine, but in fact

we had so many other problems to deal with, such as the density of children in the playground, noise, heat, gender issues, and the fact that the ball sports area really took up the whole yard and meant that other groups were relegated to the surrounding area. In fact, these were things that are fundamental and a priority for a schoolyard, but which were perhaps not directly part of the basic scope of Brussels Environnement, which said we'd just do planted areas and water, if I may caricature a little...We quickly realized in the course of our work that, in the end, we may have worked on a lot more axes than those two, perhaps even making choices at times, saying that we're not going as far with permeability and revegetation, because there are other, even more important issues to deal with."

Other subcontracted actors made similar observations, noting the significant social component of the project necessitated addressing concerns beyond purely environmental aims. For instance, 21 Solutions emphasized that "one of the key objectives is to combat climate change, and in particular to combat heat islands" while also recognizing that "the project had a strong social side." Meanwhile, Tournesol-Zonnebloem viewed the primary goal as "the child's well-being...from a physical point of view, the freshness of the yard and all that, but also from a mental [well-being] point of view."

Discord in Project Expectations

The differences in the goals and intentions behind the project occasionally resulted in tensions between the schools and Brussels Environment, leading to friction. Architects noted that some schools arrived with visions that diverged from the project's ecological focus, often prioritizing aesthetic concerns or a calling for basic needs to be met like functioning toilets and water fountains. This led to confusion about why they couldn't be included in Opération Ré-création, illustrating the misalignment between the schools' expectation and the overarching goals set by Brussels Environment.

At School D, there was discernible tension between the objectives of Opération Ré-création and those of the school's existing garden initiative. One teacher, who leads the garden project, was particularly intent on preserving the garden's food theme. This teacher perceived Brussels Environment's plan as potentially turning the yard into "a little park in the school," (T1D) which, in their view, prioritized BE's agenda over the school's desires.

Interviews reveal that, despite the project's primary ecological goals, there is also a shared understanding that the initiative must address broader social elements to achieve the desired 'exemplary' status. The architects discussed the need for a balanced approach, describing their efforts to comprehensively renovate the yard, "facade to facade," addressing various organization challenges. They emphasized that merely adding small pockets of vegetation would not resolve the underlying issues plaguing schoolyards.

Many schools communicated a desire for a *préau* (an outdoor covering for a playground), driven by the challenge of organizing outdoor time in a rainy climate. This feature often proves costly and falls outside the scope of climate and ecological improvements. The disagreement over the *préau* epitomizes the tension between the practical needs of schools and the objectives of BE. An interviewee from Brussels Environment articulated this, describing how “we come with a comprehensive project that's accompanied by the architect. So you're not going to be able to ask us for a *préau*. You see, in Belgium, all schools want a *préau* so that children can go outside during recess and not get soaked. We said no” (BE2).

Although Brussels Environment aimed to demonstrate potential and possibility without financial limitations, budgetary constraints inevitably influenced the project's outcome. Several interviewees highlighted the friction between ambitious goals and financial realities, noting the complex dynamic between Brussels Environment as the funder and the schools as recipients. Project leaders at Brussels Environment acknowledged the schools' desires while trying to establish clear guidelines aligned with their own priorities. Many teachers and directors expressed their understanding and appreciation of the project, particularly noting the relief of not having to finance the project themselves.

So many of these disappointments, frustrations, and tensions can be traced back to the way expectations were set and communicated at the start of the project. One teacher at School B expressed a desire for Brussels Environment to have better introduced itself, the project, and the various stakeholders from the beginning, outlining the different steps, activities, and processes involved. Architects were also surprised by the schools' apparent lack of awareness regarding the scope of the project, questioning whether the schools fully understood their commitments: “Do you realize that you're going to have a construction site for a long time? Do you realize that you're going to have to provide maintenance? Do you realize that you're going to have to live differently in a schoolyard, and anticipate your education differently too? Managing children in contact with nature?”

Communication Between Actors

Communication emerged as a critical theme across interviews, with many participants commenting on how communication within their schools, with Brussels Environment, and among subcontractors either facilitated or hindered the project. The context within each school varied considerably, reflecting differences in the relationships between teachers and directors, as well as the involvement of parents. A representative from OSMOS noted that “the governance of each school was quite different. In some cases you had a director that was very collaborative, in other cases the headmaster or headmistress was very forceful in their nature.”

In some schools, existing channels facilitate communication, such as a dedicated 'eco team' serving as a foundation for discussions about OR, or regularly scheduled meetings allowing for ongoing conversations about the project. Generally, the director acted as the primary conduit of information, and in schools where directors prioritized communication, there was a broader understanding and more unified vision of the project.

School B stood out as making communication a key priority within the school's project management. Teachers overwhelmingly praised the level of information sharing, noting "we've always been kept informed, we've always had our say" (T4B). According to the school's director, teachers in the OR working group were charged with serving "as relays, not only for the children... but also for the other teachers." Teachers voluntarily joined the workgroup, with the director acknowledging that not all teachers could be so deeply involved. Those who did join, willingly accepted the responsibility to keep their colleagues informed, participating in meetings and workshops with the explicit purpose of "giving feedback to the teachers who weren't there" (T1B.) The director also emphasized the importance of maintaining communication with the parents, stating, "it's interesting to communicate where we are in terms of the process and what's happening with the children." Parents interviewed from the school noted that they "always felt that we've been very involved and informed," receiving emails from the school at least every three months with updates on Opération Ré-création's progress, and opportunities to participate (P1B).

In contrast, at School C, most of the information was disseminated directly from the director, who served as the primary point of contact for any questions, and the "intermediary" between internal and external actors (T2C). The school also did not explicitly engage parents during the design process, with one teacher acknowledging, "It's true that one of the points we gave the least thought to was involving parents," opting instead to "wait for it to become concrete" before establishing active communication channels (T2C). The schoolyard plan was posted at the school's entrance for parents and others to see, with the intent to gradually involve parents, and "to explain to them that, yes, we'll be undergoing work for a year, and that afterwards, the playground will look like something completely different, and that it will indeed change things" (T2C).

At School A, conflicts among school staff hindered communication, exacerbating disputes. Tensions emerged between the director, the concierge, and teachers, with a teacher noting that for any decisions, "unfortunately, we have to go through a hierarchy" (T1A). The same teacher candidly expressed that, "the problem is this, Mr. Director, has a lot of things to think about at the same time, and he may not be sharing everything as he should," pointing to a clear divide within the school community (T1A). That disconnect was also observed by the architects, who noted how "the whole school was also having problems with its

management” leading to “the feeling that these were much more structural problems, which ultimately found in the playground project a way to vent all the other worries they had internally.”

Governance Structure & Decision Making

As Opération Ré-création progresses, the increasing involvement of various stakeholders contributes to the project’s complexity, enriching it while also introducing additional opportunities for confusion and miscommunication. Brussels Environment intentionally designed an extensive network of actors – including two consortia comprising architects, ecologists, and numerous construction firms – with the intention of distributing responsibility. This strategy aimed to ensure that the project would not hinge on any singular player. According to Brussels Environment, this approach was intended as a safeguard, “because it's fragmented, because nobody has everything, but everybody knows a little bit about what the others are doing. If one architect quits tomorrow, I've got another” (BE2).

From the perspective of the participating schools, many educators found the intricate network of stakeholders to be confusing, complicated, and challenging to navigate, though not all shared this sentiment. Observations from workshops within schools indicated that many teachers were not well-informed about the project’s status and often lacked clarity regarding whom to approach with their inquiries. At School C, for example, during a workshop it was observed that only one member of the OR workgroup, along with the director, and municipal representative, had a comprehensive understanding of the project status, leaving the other teachers somewhat disoriented. At School A, only a handful of teachers appeared informed about the project. At one point, the school’s director asked a technical question to a representative from 21 Solutions, indicating a lack of clarity on how to contact the architects responsible for the query.

Tournesol-Zonnenbloem also observed this issue, noting that schools often approached them with questions they were ill-equipped to answer. This general state of confusion led to frustration among some teachers. One educator remarked, “I've completely lost myself in all [the actors],” and further expressed how the project’s organization was somewhat inadequate, stating “What's the connection with everyone? It got lost very quickly...It was a bit complex. I think it was a bit poorly organized. I don't think it was structured” (T2B). This teacher suggested that a clearer presentation of all the actors and their roles, along with a structured diagram or document, would have been beneficial.

Not all teachers viewed the extensive networks of actors negatively. One teacher appreciated the depth of the organizational network, stating, “There's a whole organization around it. So I found that very rich, and all the help from the various ASBLs that came into

the project, I think they were important” (T1B). This teacher indicated that precise knowledge of each individual’s role was less critical, provided they “knew the first names, the person's face. It wasn't that important to know exactly where they were from” (T1B). Similarly, another teacher noted, “No, it didn't bother us because in the end, we were able to get answers to our questions, so it wasn't a big deal” (T2C).

The trend in responses suggests that teachers more deeply involved in the project, particularly those in leadership roles within their workgroups, had a better grasp of various stakeholders. However, this understanding did not always extend to other members of the workgroup or the broader school staff.

A few interviewees expressed a desire for increased interaction with representatives from other schools, especially as construction progresses. In response to this need, Brussels Environment organized an annual event bringing together all the schools, their organizing authorities, and other stakeholders. A project leader from Brussels Environment described these events as “great,” observing that “you can see that the teachers are inspiring each other, enthusiastic and impatient” (BE1).

Project Timeline & Delays

One of the most prevalent issues raised during interviews pertained to a lack of clarity regarding the project’s delay. The initial timeline specified in the call for proposals anticipated completion by 2023; however, this project was at odds with the realities of budgetary constraints and challenges in securing contracts with construction firms. These factors have extended the project’s timeline by up to a year in some cases. One teacher noted that the timeline “wasn't communicated” (T1C). Various educators expressed uncertainty, with one saying, “I think they keep postponing it. We were told we might start in January, but now it might be this summer, I think it's been postponed again” (T2C). A parent similarly expressed, “As long as it hasn't started, it hasn't started” (P2B).

The significant disappointment regarding the extended timeline is largely attributed to expectation management, particularly among students who participated in the project but will not be present to witness its completion. The disappointment among older students is frequently highlighted in interviews, with nearly all respondents describing the regret students feel about not experiencing the final yard. Teachers and directors described their students frustration:

“Some of the older children are a little disappointed, because they think they'll never see the finished yard.” (Teacher 1, School C)

“There are children who have already left school and were expecting the playground, but didn't see it. So it's true that those in sixth grade are saying, “Well, we won't see it. Those in sixth are keeping their fingers crossed, saying ‘Ah, will we get the chance to...’ because they realize that this isn't a small job and that it takes time.” (Teacher 1, School B)

“The students who helped set up the project, especially those who were in grades 5-6 with us, have left or are leaving, so they won't see the end of what they've set up.” (Teacher 1, School D)

“What's just a bit of a shame is that the primary 5 or 6 students who took part in this participative work will see the benefits later, when they may no longer be at the school.” (Director 1, School D)

“So it's true that some of the children who took part in developing the project are no longer at the school and they think it's a shame because they were able to give their ideas, share them and then won't be able to see the end result.” (Teacher 2, School C)

“Those who really decided on the yard for the children have already left, unfortunately for them.” (Teacher 1, School A)

“There are children who took part at the start of the project, who are no longer in the school and who regretted saying to themselves...we'll never see this yard” (Teacher 2, School C)

Parents echo similar sentiments, with one parent stating, “My eldest said we'd never see the playground...but even the two little ones I'm not sure they'll ever see it” (P2B). Students also openly express their disappointment and question the protracted process:

“[Student 1] I don't know when we'll get it. [Student 2] But we sixth graders won't be able to have that experience because we won't be there.” (School D)

“That's a pity because we won't be here. We won't be here anymore.” (School C)

“Well, for us it's a long time because we won't get to know the yard for very long. We should have known the yard for at least two years.” (School B)

Many adults within the schools also express disappointment, often describing a sensation of helplessness during the process. One teacher conveyed this sentiment, stating, “there's

nothing we can do” (T1C), while another remarked, “I found that was the biggest obstacle, because we were just...well...helpless, really” (T3B). Adults generally demonstrated a greater understanding of the delays compared to students, with one teacher explaining, “When you're an adult, it's something you can understand. But for a child, it's more difficult. It's hard for a child to understand that it's not going to happen right away” (T2C).

At St. Trinite, the first school to begin construction, it was noted, “We've been waiting for a few months. Normally, the yard should have been done by the end of 2023, I think. But in the end, it's being done now [2024/2025]” (T2B). Despite the prevailing negative feelings about the delays, many comments conclude with a note of enthusiasm for the project feelings and justification for the delay:

“I'm really looking forward to it starting now. Because it was supposed to start last year, so every time it's delayed. I feel like we've been talking about it for two years now, so it would be good to move forward and see it through.” (Teacher 1, School C)

“Honestly, I think it may be a rather long project, but I think it's been a good one.” (Afterschool Coordinator, School B)

“It's true that here, at the end of the process, there has been a bit of a delay. Each time, a deadline was added. I think it's been a year, maybe a year and a half. We're told that the work has started, but it hasn't. So we're really starting to get excited.” (Teacher 2, School C)

The more teachers and school staff understood the reasons behind the delays, the more accepting they became of the revised timeline, underscoring the importance of communication during unforeseen changes. Most delays were attributed to issues with the call for construction companies because of inflation and the subsequent need to adapt plans. Teachers recognized that “this was the most complicated part, because it was purely budgetary, and there was nothing we could do about it. In fact, there was nothing anyone could do. Someone had to respond to our project” (T3B). A director added, “We're still waiting for authorizations. So, it's out of our hands. We're waiting for signatures from higher up” (D1D).

Architects commented on the potential impact of these delays on the overall motivation for Opération Ré-création within schools. According to them, the “risk with the motivation curve,” arises when “the school is waiting, they've done some intense participative work, and then for a year they're thinking, what's going on? So it's difficult to try and maintain the positive momentum, but you know it's going to come back with the worksite.”

5.6 Participatory Process

Preliminary Participation Phase: Raising Awareness

Moving to the second research question, we can unpack the nuances throughout the participation process to understand *how the feedback from the co-creation process translated into a strategic plan to be implemented in the final product.*

The initial phase of the project began with Brussels Environment meeting and explaining the project to workgroups at each of the 19 schools, and established the importance of the project. Tournesol-Zonnenbloem, serving as the primary liaison with schools, organized a day involving a group of student delegates, beginning with a morning workshop in the schoolyard aimed at raising awareness about the importance of greening. During this workshop, concepts such as heat islands, green-blue networks, and permeability were introduced. Students were encouraged to express their likes, dislikes, and desired changes for their schoolyard. A teacher from School C noted the effectiveness of the activity, remarking:

“They had come on a rainy day and we had noticed that the yard flooded very, very quickly. And so the children were wondering why, and it was great because they explained to the children that it was because the earth couldn't absorb it. So it was a really interesting and thought-provoking discussion for both the children and the adults” (Teacher 2, School C)

Additionally, a biodiversity audit was conducted to evaluate the yard's capacity to support various species by examining existing planter beds, dead tree logs, and little crevices in the wall.

The afternoon session focused on exploring students' vision for their yard. To inspire creativity and transcend traditional perceptions of a schoolyard, Tournesol employed the pedagogical tool Pic2school, a set of pictograms representing various elements that students could choose from (fig. 22). Each pictogram was assigned a value between one and four points, reflecting criteria such as environmental impact, spatial requirements relative to the number of students served, and real financial cost. Students received four tokens each and were required to collaboratively allocate their tokens to 'purchase' different pictograms. Some items, such as a ball zone, were most costly, requiring a collective pooling of tokens, while others, like landscaping elements, were less expensive. Student groups adopted different strategies, with some opting to acquire numerous, less expensive items, while others concentrated their tokens on fewer, most costly features.

Figure 22: Pictograms used by Tournesol-Zonnebloem (Source: Bubble Brussels)

The strategy proved effective with younger students as well, and a pre-primary teacher recounted using the pictograms with two to three year old students, noting how it allowed “those who know how to express themselves to express themselves” (T1B). The diversity in ages across workshop participants added an extra layer to the learning experience. A workshop leader from Tournesol-Zonnebloem observed, “the older kids had a lot to learn, especially when it came to listening to what the younger ones wanted. Maybe also because the older ones knew they wouldn't be around when we were setting up. I think they had a harder time negotiating, perhaps with the 2nd and 3rd graders, who are a bit in between.”

Including participants of all ages was essential for ensuring the project addressed the needs of the entire school community, rather than focusing solely on younger students. One teacher observed that while elementary school students requested amenities like “slides,

benches, sandboxes, bike circuit, ball fields,” secondary school students preferred spaces to “isolate themselves” like “a grassy area where certain students can go to recharge their batteries” (T1D).

A director emphasized the importance of Tournesol-Zonnebloem’s work, stating, “we didn't want it to be biased by us either, our desires. Here, it's someone from the outside who's bringing out what the kids want, and we have to take that into account...We're not the ones who decide, so it's really the children who decide, and so having someone from the outside helps to encourage the children's real desires” (DB).

With the adults, Tournesol-Zonnebloem and 21 Solutions, conducted a diagnostic of the existing yard and presented inspirational images of other green schoolyards, allowing the school community – including teachers, directors, maintenance staff, and parents – to provide input. During this process, many teachers already saw the designs and preferences of the students, and often supported the children’s preferences. One teacher described these compromises between teachers and students, stating how some elements “were abandoned, and things that the teachers didn't think were of primary importance, have been kept because they were very important to the children” (T1B). Tournesol-Zonnebloem critiqued the lack of follow-up after the initial engagement with the adults, feeling their role concluded prematurely.

Finally, Écorce synthesized the preferences of students and teachers into a preliminary plan, which was then subject to validation by school administrators before sending it to the architect. This initial sketch, created by Écorce and Tournesol-Zonnebloem, served as a foundation for the architects to build upon, rather than a final design.

Second Round: Development of Final Plan

The architects then took over the design process, building on the participatory work conducted by Tournesol-Zonnebloem and the preliminary sketch by Écorce. This process unfolded in four steps. The first step, the preliminary project, *avant projet*, expanded upon the initial sketch using ideas from the initial participation phase to create a draft. The architects began with a diagnostic of the current situation, acknowledging that Tournesol-Zonnebloem had “already done a bit of this during the pre-accompaniment phase, but we went back over it ourselves to get our own take on things.”

In the second phase, children were involved through a system of delegates, asking *what do you want* and *what do you need* from your new yard. The proposed layout was presented back to the schools and validated through four to five additional participatory workshops with the delegates over a period of 18 months. The third phase involved refining this proposal based on feedback, creating a concrete plan.

These first three phases – avant projet, delegate meetings, and concrete proposal – were described by the architects as stages for “completely open dreaming,” meant to “organize wishes and desires, and then we look precisely at how we spatialize, and we go into questions of greater detail, materials, play and choice.” The architects engaged in iterative discussions with schools, typically involving directors and Brussels Environment, to adjust the plans in alignment with the school’s priorities and ecological needs (e.g. flood prevention). Once the final plans were approved, the architects prepared cost estimates for the call for construction companies.

The fourth phase involved presenting the final design through an exhibition, meant to give schools a chance to really appropriate their future yard. Architects created posters explaining the process and rationale behind the final plan, and trained teachers and students to present this information to the public. These posters were displayed in schools for extended periods, allowing parents to learn about the project.

Critiques of this second round of participatory design included concerns about the architects’ dual reporting to Brussels Environment and the schools, which occasionally caused confusion. To address this, future iterations of Opération Ré-création schoolyard transformations plan to involve architects from the outset to streamline information sharing and reduce duplication of effort between Tournesol-Zonnebloem and the architects.

Students Perceptions of the Participative Process

When questioned about their roles and perceptions of the participative process, students overwhelmingly provided positive feedback, vividly recalling their involvement:

“We did lots of little workshops. And inside, at one point, they put cards on the table and we had to choose just one thing we wanted to put in the playground. We could choose teepees, wooden modules, an amphitheater, you name it.” (School B)

“We played a game and had a piece of paper where we said what we wanted. But we each had five points and if we chose a photo, we had to give a point for that. And everyone gave their idea.” (School D)

“They showed us photos of other yards. And we said whether we liked it or not.” (School D)

“In fact, every class has already talked about the yard. I did it with my class. Everyone had come up with ideas. Some said what was good and what was bad for the yard.” (School C)

“What I remember is that when we were doing the activities, at one point they gave us nuggets, a gold colored thing. And then there were all the things we wanted. There were cabins, a pond. There were things like that. And then the nuggets, you could choose whatever you wanted. I think we only had 6 or 11 gold nuggets. For example, the hut was 5 nuggets and we could choose. I remember we chose a pond over there, on that side.” (School C)

“I remember we did an experiment with hourglasses. In one hourglass, we put stone. In another, earth. And the other, I think, was sand. Then we put water in to see which one would go down faster. To see if we put earth or stones. We chose earth because it goes down faster.” (School C)

The students not only recounted positive memories of the involvement, but expressed an appreciation for being included and listened to during the decision-making process. They felt their ideas were important and distinct from those of adults, as one student remarked, “the kids are going to use the yard, so they're going to ask for things they'd like to have, and that's great. Adults don't have to decide everything on their own, because if they take our place, maybe we won't like it.” For many students, this participative process represented an opportunity for active involvement in shaping their environment, unlike other times when, as one student at School B observed, “we don't have a choice and we have to do it,” though another added, “Yes, but we're just kids.” Similar sentiments were echoed by students at School C, who noted that if teachers made decisions alone, “maybe they'll choose things we didn't want” and emphasized, “We know what kids like.”

Adults within the school community shared this positive assessment, viewing the inclusion of children in the process as one of the most valuable and essential aspects of Opération Ré-création. One teacher specifically praised the use of the pictograms in spurring imagination, calling the process “very enriching” because the “children were able to go into greater depth to choose elements that were really important to them” (T1B). Another teacher described how the kids “couldn't wait” to participate and we're excited to share their voice because “I don't think they were very happy with the playground as it is now” (T2C).

Through this process several consistent priorities emerged among the students, including a desire for animals, calm spaces, additional activities, and places to hide, play sports, and seek shade. Students from School D described wanting “more places to play hide and seek,” a “sports field,” “more games,” “tunnels,” “places to chat with benches,” and “quiet places to read a book.” Children showed enthusiasm for elements that aligned with the climate goals of Opération Ré-création, such as trees to “sit under” and “protect yourself

from the sun when it's too hot," noting that trees would attract "more birds" and provide "air." One student highlighted the practical need for shade, observing that "when we eat chocolate, it melts." Other priorities included the desire for "trash bins, that way the yard always stays clean," and additional space to store bikes.

Students expressed mixed feelings about a school garden, with greater enthusiasm from kids at School D, where a garden is already in place, who liked the idea because they "like nature" and find it "very cool."

Some concerns were raised about whether the children's expectations for the yard were realistic, which underscored the importance of the participatory workshops in balancing the students' aspirations with practical limitations. For instance, while some students at School C wanted a treehouse, this idea was ultimately excluded to ensure the design remained feasible and easy to maintain.

Effective communication played a crucial role in managing these expectations, ensuring students had a realistic understanding of what could be achieved. A teacher explained that while the children initially had some "far-fetched ideas...when we explained to them the aim of the project and obviously the things that could and couldn't be done, they understood and weren't frustrated" (T2C). Similarly, a director noted that "the students know very well that you can't put everything in there and that you have to prioritize certain things" (DB).

In the end, even though not all their ideas could be incorporated into the final plans, the students were "just happy there's change" (T3B). Overall, the children expressed satisfaction with the final plans, indicating pride with their school, with one student noting, "I think we're going to be the only school to have this. In all the schools I've seen, there's no school that has this." During an interview with students, upon seeing the final plans for the first time, students excitedly exclaimed, "Oh it's going to be beautiful!" Declaring, "if the yard is going to be this beautiful, I'm going to try and repeat a year, so I can stay there for the rest of my life." A few concerns were also voiced, such as the fear that the yard might be too crowded with greenery, making it smaller and potentially leading to more disputes.

Teachers across all four schools agreed that the students' ideas were genuinely considered, with one teacher noting, "At the kids level, it was super well respected. They will find everything they wanted" (T3B), and another describing the process as "a form of democracy that was pretty remarkable" (T1A).

Adult Perceptions of the Participative Process

The adults also describe the participative process positively, with some noting that it reignited their own sense of childhood wonder, “I think we all become kids again with our desires” (T1C). One significant variation between the participative process at different schools was the inclusion of various adult actors. Some schools found it highly beneficial to involve cleaning staff in the discussions, as one director noted, “we had to know what type of materials was going to be selected [and] how to maintain [them]” (D2D).

Schools were less consistent in including parents during the design phase. At both Schools C & D, few parents participated despite intentions to involve them. At School D, they “opened the door” to parents, and only one or two participated. School C, lacking a parents’ association, did not formally invite parents to join the discussions, with one speculating whether this was due to insufficient invitations or a lack of interest. The same teacher observed that “parents are less and less involved in schools in general...between covid and the attacks, parents can no longer enter schools for security reasons” (T2C). In contrast, at School B, parents voted on their preferences alongside teachers and students, with one parent expressing “I really appreciated having the opportunity to participate” (P1B). Brussels Environment noted that independent schools often require more support, leading to greater parental involvement in school life.

Through the discussions among various adult actors, the main priorities for schoolyard design often centered on the intersection of quality of life and environmental benefits. Frequent comments concerning broken, hard flooring material causing trips and “omnipresent puddles,” leading to a preference for softer material and improved rainwater management (T1B). Teachers also identified the lack of nature and excess heat as issues to be addressed. Both students and teachers consistently requested space for outdoor learning.

Reflecting on the process, one teacher noted how their main concern was carefully integrated into the plan, “even our comments about the flooding..were taken into account..Now, it's all been taken care of. We could see that the plan was evolving in line with our comments” (T1C). Overall, no interviewee from the four schools expressed dissatisfaction with how the final plans reflected the participatory workshops. Moreover, teachers from multiple schools articulated how they felt the process had genuinely included everyone in their school community, not just a token group.

“What I really liked, was that they took into account every person in the school”
(Teacher 1, School B)

“They were really pretty open to our ideas. They really listened to everyone, all the factors and all the school players.” (Teacher 2, School B)

“What I think was good was to implicate everyone. That was really cool. Everyone had their moment to say their word.” (Teacher 1, School C)

“I thought it was great to see that they'd taken everything we'd discussed into account, but also to see the other little ideas that had been added.” (Teacher 2, School C)

A few critical points emerged during interviews. A teacher at School B expressed a desire for a dedicated session at the beginning of the process for teachers to have a more in depth discussion about the day-to-day realities, noting that some tasks “will only fall on the teachers” (T3B). At School A, one teacher mentioned that in retrospect they would've preferred some training about how to present and facilitate discussions with the delegates in the classroom. Additionally, conflict arose at School A during the design phase, with disagreements among teachers regarding the differing needs of the youngest compared to the rest of the student body.

Emerging Themes

Concerns frequently arose regarding the domination of sports in outdoor spaces and the resulting boredom experienced by students, leading to conflicts due to the monotony of the concrete yards. Many of these issues are rooted in broader discussions about risk, necessitating a reevaluation of what is traditionally considered hazardous.

Some parents and teachers expressed concerns about the safety of greened yards, such as plants and bushes obstructing views necessary for supervising children, the potential for children to get dirty, slip on wet grass, or water leading to falls. However, upon closer examination and reflection on the current yards, a number of teachers and students highlighted existing safety issues that already place students at risk.

Nearly every interviewee noted the dangers posed by concrete surfaces, which in many schools are often cracked and uneven, causing frequent accidents during outdoor play. One student remarked, “I don't like being outside too much because we can fall” (School D). At the same school, a beloved walnut tree was cut down due to the perceived danger of slipping on the nuts, rather than addressing the many falls caused by broken floor tiles. This example illustrates the disproportionate perception of the risks posed by natural elements.

These concerns can be reframed, shifting to view the new, more engaging yard, as a place that will “enable the children, instead of coming to talk to us about arguments, to come and talk to us about the things they've discovered,” creating “a moment of exchange rather than a moment of real supervision” (T2C).

Reevaluating the risks associated with the traditional organization of schoolyards, where sports typically overtake the central area, also highlights the potential benefits of greened schoolyards. Most schools previously attempted to create zones and schedules to mitigate the influence of ball games, but with limited alternative activities, students have often resisted these restrictions.

Sports contribute to disputes for two primary reasons. Firstly, the games themselves often lead to conflicts among students over rules. One student noted, “when we play soccer, they hit and hurt each other, and it ends in a fight” (School C). Secondly, the emphasis on sports can marginalize a significant portion of the student body, leading to boredom, which can result in conflicts.

Some students observed that the fixation on sports is partly due to the lack of alternative play options. With the new yard design, they anticipate that sports will become less centralized, not only in terms of physical space but also because, as one student pointed out, “there will be more game ideas and things to do. We can't play hide and seek now because we don't have a lot of hiding spots. With the new yard we'll have lots” (School D).

The transformation plans do not entirely eliminate sports but instead rethink and reorganize them. All schools plan to maintain a designated area for ball games but intend to decentralize that space and introduce a “calm zone” and an “activity zone without ball games” to diversify play opportunities. At School C, students noted that basketball hoops were located above the soccer goals, meaning only one sport could be played at a time, which caused disappointment, anticipating a potential source of conflict. One director speculated that the new yard, “Will be much more serene than the yard we have now. Now, it's more a yard that creates conflicts because the children don't have anything else to do other than play ball” (DB). Another teacher mentioned that the redesigned yard would allow children to “either seek calm or play ball without being disturbed by others who'd like to climb or do other things” (T1B). Overall, these transformations signify a crucial shift in how schoolyards are conceptualized, prioritizing a more balanced and inclusive approach to student play and well-being.

5.7 Construction

Turning to the third and fourth research questions, the research evaluates the needs and concerns expressed by interviewees to anticipate future challenges, seeking to understand *what key knowledge and skills schools need to effectively manage and maintain their schoolyard*. While looking further so speculate *how the integration of the schoolyard into educational practices and community partnerships can enhance broader impact*.

The unique process for contracting construction companies in Brussels is a consequence of the city's complex educational structure. The organizing authorities, sometimes in collaboration with school directors, were tasked with publishing a call for proposals and hiring contractors to execute the plans developed and budgeted by the architects. In municipal schools, the organizing authority – the municipality – launches the construction market, with the project often simultaneously followed by an architect from the municipality. Conversely, independent schools, like School B, require more extensive support from architects in drafting technical clauses, because their organizing authority typically lacks experience with such procedures.

To mitigate risks throughout this process, schools receive guidance from a representative of Brussels Environment. They assist in drafting the call for contractors, negotiating budgets, and overseeing construction sites. Ultimately, the choice of contractor rests with the school. As a representative from Brussels Environment said, “if they take the cheaper one and the worst one, we'll have to do it with them. It's their responsibility” (BE3).

During the call for builders, a number of surprises delayed the process. Schools received fewer responses than anticipated, and the bids were much higher than the allocated subsidies. Although each school receives a fixed budget, efforts were made to allocate additional funds to schools facing particular constraints, such as more complex logistical challenges. For instance, Brussels Environment explained that at a certain school construction costs were higher because access to the yard required passage through the school building, unlike schools where construction vehicles could directly access the site. This variation in funding illustrates that the process is “not a question of equality, it's a question of adapting to these contexts” (BE3).

According to Brussels Environment, the designs are changing following the participative process to accommodate changing budgets. Elements removed from the plans mostly included “accessories” that schools could add later on, like smaller plants, games, and benches. Brussels Environment ensured the major renovations, like planting large trees and installing flooring, remained intact, while seeking creative ways of sourcing other elements.

At School B, where the revised plans are finalized, a teacher remarked how “not much, to me, disappeared” (T1B).

A significant challenge during construction, which typically lasts between three and six months, sometimes more, is how schools will function with limited access to their yards. Architects attempted to anticipate and minimize disruptions by advising schools on how to manage during construction.

In interviews, school staff frequently cited this issue as their most pressing concern. Each school is developing its own strategies to cope, depending on the timing of construction and the available space. At School B, the municipality plans to close off the street in front of the school to provide additional space for students. However, several members of the school community described this solution as “very complicated” (T5B) and “very difficult” (DB) due to the limited space, which necessitates dividing students between the street and the gym, requiring extra staff for supervision.

At School C, construction occurs in two phases, ensuring a portion of the yard remains open. Construction, originally slated for July 2024 is pushed back to late August 2024, a change that surprised the director when revealed during a workshop. This unexpected timing means the school will have to adapt to a louder, more disruptive environment. During participative workshops with 21 Solutions, schools considered forming potential partnerships during construction, like using the neighboring school’s yard, or a local sports center, though teachers pointed to obstacles of funding and timing.

Despite these concerns, the overwhelming enthusiasm for the project remains strong. Teachers frequently expressed that “it’s the price to pay to have an easier life in the yard,” and acknowledged that, ultimately, the improvements will be with the temporary inconvenience (T1B).

5.8 Maintenance

Maintenance is a pivotal element in ensuring the long-term success of greening schoolyards. The effectiveness of maintenance strategies, and the manner in which schools are supported in managing their greenspaces, is crucial to achieving sustainable outcomes. Inadequate maintenance can result in deteriorating vegetation and loss of motivation within the school community, underscoring the importance of proactive planning.

Among the schools involved in Opération Ré-création, there is a broad consensus that formulating a maintenance plan is challenging without first experiencing the completed yard. Concerns about finalizing construction contracts and managing school days with an active worksite diverts attention from longer-term planning. Interviewed school staff

frequently described the concept of maintenance planning as, “ambiguous,” “vague,” (T1B) “unknown,” “difficult to anticipate” (T1C) primarily due to the uncertainty about the specific features of the yard. One director remarked, “It’ll be time to think when we see,” and addressed potential difficulties by stating, “If we think about the obstacles, I don't think we're making any headway. There are bound to be obstacles, but we have to keep going and stay the course” (D1D). Another director expressed how their team is approaching maintenance with a mindset of “trial and error” (D2D).

Both ÁRTER and 21 Solutions acknowledged the inherent uncertainty surrounding maintenance, noting that it is premature to discuss detailed plans before the yard’s completion. They agreed that once schools experience and appropriate the new yards, they will be better positioned to manage maintenance.

To aid in this transition, contracts with the construction companies include a maintenance guarantee for two yards, where contractors are responsible for routine maintenance tasks, such as tending to garden beds and inspecting play structures. This arrangement is intended to support schools, with contractors modeling effective maintenance practices. However, this guarantee does not absolve schools from responsibility for their own maintenance errors, such as overwatering, requiring a certain level of training to be in place from the start. Additionally, Brussels Environment will conduct biannual visits to each school, Écorce will monitor the schools and offer maintenance advice, and Tournesol-Zonnenbloem will provide training sessions of specific maintenance issues upon request.

Several concerns about maintenance emerged during interviews, including teachers’ lack of gardening knowledge and the time commitment required. Teachers also expressed apprehension about maintaining care during school holidays. Some schools host camps during the summer who could provide assistance, or alternatively, create a schedule for staff to come in on a rotating basis. In School D’s existing vegetable garden, they adjust planting schedules to optimize harvest in the spring and fall, and two individuals assist for bi-weekly summer maintenance.

Specific concerns include disputes with the concierge at School A, who is unwilling to let people into the building outside of school hours. Other schools point to the logistical difficulties in engaging parents for maintenance tasks, like language barriers, time constraints, and cultural differences. Despite these challenges, schools with active parents’ associations appear more optimistic about mobilizing parental support.

Several interviewees expressed concerns about the lack of maintenance budgets, highlighting the financial burden associated with the upkeep of renovated schoolyards. The

general consensus is that maintaining these spaces will necessitate additional funds, which many schools do not possess. A teacher at School D candidly expressed skepticism about the sustainability of Opération Ré-création, stating, “It won’t work. Why? Because the plants will grow and in five years we’ll have to maintain them. Who will do it? With what budget? There isn’t one” (T1D).

Given the constraints of their budgets, schools are tasked with organizing maintenance labor, involving both internal and external volunteers. Typically, schools expect teachers to undertake daily maintenance tasks, although there is no mandate for teachers to do so. Interviews with members of Opération Ré-création workgroups at their respective schools, revealed a hope that the majority of teachers will contribute to maintenance efforts, but concerns persist that the majority of work may ultimately fall to a small group of individuals. One teacher noted, “We can’t see ourselves doing all the work on our own,” (T1B) while another worried that the most motivated individuals might “run out of steam” (T3B). Generally, a few noted that teachers not directly involved in Opération Ré-création might be unclear about their responsibilities, so “they’re a bit on edge and walking on eggshells because they don’t know what to expect” (T1B).

Teachers discussed various strategies for integrating maintenance into school routines through pedagogic activities or aligning with an existing group, like eco-teams. Some workshops explored organizational structures for maintenance, including rotating responsibilities among classes, or assigning specific areas of the yard to each class. The general consensus is that maintenance must be approached as a collaborative effort to ensure its sustainability.

Students also demonstrated enthusiasm for participating in maintenance, with potential to integrate maintenance into regular student activities. Suggestions include creating engaging activities like gathering and putting back wood chips, using mini blowers to clear leaves, and weeding garden beds. However, establishing these practices as routines will take time. Not all students are keen to participate, with one student commenting “you’re not even sure you’re taking good care of it. So if you don’t take good care of it, maybe it’s a bit of a waste” (School B).

Each school typically designates at least one individual, such as a concierge or janitor, to oversee maintenance and routine care. Technical tasks, like pruning trees, are generally not expected to be performed by school staff and are instead assigned to external professionals. Basic maintenance tasks like trimming hedges and removing debris usually fall within the responsibilities of the cleaning staff.

Municipal schools theoretically benefit from support, with the expectation that municipalities will provide gardeners and possibly demonstrate maintenance practices. School C relies on municipal assistance, although the municipality lacks experience with green schoolyards, making it a learning process for them as well. Interviewees from Brussels Environment noted that municipalities are overworked and understaffed, resulting in less availability than anticipated. A concern is that the maintenance of school gardens differs from that of traditional gardens, requiring specialized knowledge of the pedagogical aspects of the garden's design. Brussels Environment noted that external gardeners can be problematic if they lack familiarity with the project, and may inadvertently damage or remove essential features.

In contrast, independent schools manage their maintenance autonomously, either through their own staff or by hiring external help. The architects didn't view this as particularly concerning, anticipating that independent schools will be "more proactive" compared to municipal schools, who may rely on external assistance.

To address maintenance labor gaps, many schools plan to involve parents to alleviate the burden on teachers and cleaning staff. For example, School B already engages parents in the maintenance of their vegetable garden and organizes annual craft days, with plans to extend similar initiatives to maintenance activities, such as landscaping or winter preparation.

Teachers suggested that parents are likely to be interested in participating, with one noting, "We need to set up a real partnership with parents...We want a beautiful yard because it's pleasant for our students, but parents are directly concerned because it's their children" (T3B). Parents, often residing in the neighborhood, may be more available and motivated to contribute, and those from schools with more active parents' associations seem more confident in their ability to mobilize parental support.

However, the two interviewed parents expressed limited enthusiasm for regular involvement. One parent suggested students work on the yard as an afterschool activity since "I don't necessarily have the time" (P2B). Another parent was willing to assist but "I'm not going to propose something, but ask me if you need my help" (P1B).

Barriers to parental involvement include language differences, time constraints, security concerns, and cultural differences. A teacher from School D, with a diverse school population, highlighted these issues, questioning whether parents feel welcomed and speculating that as the school hosts additional activities around the renovated yard, parents might be more encouraged to participate. At School A, the ongoing issues with the concierge further complicate the potential for involving parents.

To mitigate these challenges and enhance the likelihood of successful maintenance, Brussels Environment is organizing several resources, including tailored maintenance guides and optional training workshops with Tournesol-Zonnenbloem. In addition, an ecological management manual, maintenance calendar, detailed care worksheets, a glossary of terms, and a responsibility chart for schools are being developed collaboratively by 21 Solutions, Tournesol-Zonnenbloem, ÁRTER, and Écorce (fig. 23). These resources complement both the ongoing monitoring by Écorce and the maintenance guarantee with the contractors.

These materials are presented at workshops with school staff to gather feedback before finalization. Teacher feedback has been generally positive regarding the clarity and usability of the guides, although concerns remain about the volume of work required and number of unfamiliar tasks. Requests for differentiated materials for students, teachers, and cleaning staff were also made.

Figure 23: Draft materials to support maintenance, My Yards Maintenance Calendar and the Calendar for the Ecological Management of My Yard (Source: 21 Solutions)

In-person training was requested by many schools to provide reassurance through hands-on learning. One teacher emphasized the value of demonstrating tasks, “Sometimes we like to be in the students’ shoes and learn. I think the best thing is to have someone come and explain things to us, and then we can do it ourselves” (T2C). The goal of training is to offer technical guidance while also alleviating concerns by demonstrating the steps involved. Architects stressed the importance of embracing the evolving nature of the project, acknowledging it’s built into the concept:

“We know that everything we plant is going to change. There will sometimes be areas that are left to develop spontaneously. But that’s no problem. Spontaneous plants are welcome. An area that’s been completely trampled...that’s just the way it is. Use is necessary, it doesn’t matter, this project will live on.”

Brussels Environment plans to allocate “credits” for schools to access training on specific maintenance topics, such as fruit tree care. This initiative is part of Opération Ré-création’s budget, which covers instructional support but not the execution of maintenance tasks, aligning with the goal of fostering school’s independence.

Most schools expressed support for additional training, although some teachers cited a preference for a mandated, school-wide approach to distribute the workload more equitably. While Brussels Environment and school directors stressed their inability to mandate teachers to participate, the architects concurred that involving a broad group of teachers is advantageous for anticipating and managing maintenance needs effectively.

5.9 Community Access

To provide enhanced support to schools, workshops conducted with 21 Solutions aim to assist schools cultivate external partnerships with local associations, businesses, and neighboring schools. These collaborations aspire to amplify the benefits of green schoolyards, while facilitating mutually advantageous solutions, such as performing maintenance tasks. Organized by 21 Solutions, these workshops are consistent with criteria of Opération Ré-création mandating schools make their yards available for certain forms of public use. During the application process, schools indicated their willingness to open their yards for public benefit by selecting the option, “I accept opening my yard to the benefit of the public,” indicating an intention to explore innovative ways to extend the advantages of greening rather than completely unrestricted access.

A complicating factor is that neither Brussels Environment nor the municipalities possess the authority to directly regulate school operations. As a result, schools have discretion over whom, how, and when they open their facilities. This contrasts with the Oasis yards, where municipal authorities control open access, manage opening and closing gates, and fund yard monitors. In Brussels, the lack of such authority makes the process of opening schoolyards riskier, with less institutional support for risk management and problem resolution.

Schools expressed considerable apprehension regarding this requirement, prompting Brussels Environment to adopt a more cautious approach to facilitate the process. Initially envisioned as a robust social initiative, the effort has evolved into a more gradual process focused on strengthening existing partnerships.

Many schools already meet the criteria of ‘sharing’ their yard without realizing it. At School B, a local association hosts afterschool daily, along with summer camps, and according to Brussels Environment “they don’t have to do more” to fulfill the requirement (BE1). The association’s organizer described their relationship with the school as “based in confidence and good communication” (T5B). Similarly, School C, hosts several associations outside regular school outside school hours, including training courses, a daycare, and a Polish school on weekends.

Some teachers and directors expressed enthusiasm about the potential community benefits of utilizing schoolyards. One teacher found the workshops with 21 Solutions “instructive,” noting “we hadn’t thought about the fact that our yard could serve other people” (T2C). A director at School D also expressed value in opening the yard for local residents, parents, and students.

Nevertheless, even those in favor acknowledged significant concerns and conditions for adopting a community-oriented approach. A director emphasized that the yard’s primary function is as a schoolyard and expressed a desire to comply with project requirements “within a very precise framework” (DB). The afterschool association organizer at School B noted the challenges of developing partnerships, describing the process as “not easy...it means opening your school to the outside world, so it’s always scary” (T5B). Another director shared “mixed feelings” about opening the yard, citing “scary” concerns about potential damage when not present, but acknowledging the benefit of providing greenspace to local residents (DC). A parent interviewed opposed opening the yard during weekdays, but supported weekend access, provided it’s “respectful” (P1B).

The few who support opening, often mentioned how their colleagues would not agree. Most interviewees expressed concerns and doubts about opening, debating how to ensure the yard is in suitable condition for students each morning, at the start of each day and how to navigate security concerns around unwanted behaviors. Teachers worry, “we don’t want to arrive on Monday morning and find that things have been vandalized, or that garbage or plants have been uprooted. We’re a little skeptical about whether the local people will really respect this yard” (T2C) and questioning, “who’s going to be responsible for closing the gates? Will the toilets remain available? Who’s going to clean them?” (T1B).

Several teachers also noted neighborhood conditions as a reason for unease, despite it being a key reason schools were prioritized for Opération Ré-création. Teachers described the neighborhoods as having, “quite a few people who are homeless or who drink alcohol and hang out in the streets there at night” (T1B), and not being “in the most serene neighborhood” (T1A). Brussels Environment shared these concerns, noting how “there are drug problems. We have to be responsible. When students come to the yard in the morning, it’s complicated for the school to have to coordinate that,” reinforcing BE’s decision to be more lenient with the opening requirement (BE1).

Workshops with 21 Solutions are designed to address these concerns directly, assisting schools in brainstorming partnerships, conducting outreach, and developing agreements for use of the space. One teacher found these workshops “reassuring” realizing that it’s not “just the people from the neighborhood coming in” (T2C).

Each school prioritize a list of potential partnerships. School A plans to build on pre-existing relationships, such as with a library for reading sessions in the park, and a local garden and senior center for maintenance support. At School B, existing partnerships with a daily afterschool and summer camp are top priority, along with other potential affiliations with a church and local retirement home, which could contribute to maintenance efforts. School C aims to start with established partnerships, including a local association that organizes summer camps, and a local social grocery store for potential support. They also want to consider the municipality as a partner, prioritizing a positive relationship with them. School D, having an established garden, already collaborates with scout groups and neighborhood associations and is exploring additional partnership opportunities.

In general, schools prefer to start with familiar relationships and gradually expand based on capacity. Many schools indicated that it is premature to formalize agreements before the completion of the yard. While most schools appear open to developing community connections within specific confines, schools remain concerned about managing access, including potential new security measures and their implications for teachers.

5.10 Pedagogical Use

The pedagogical use of the renovated yard is expected but not explicitly mandated. During the application process, schools were required to assess whether their yards currently host pedagogical activities or if there are plans to incorporate such activities in the future. The intent was to nudge schools to integrate outdoor learning into their curriculum, with Brussels Environment acknowledging, “It won’t work in every school. But we’re pointing them in that direction” (BE1). To support this integration, the design phase considered pedagogical use, incorporating features such as benches and amphitheaters to enhance outdoor learning opportunities.

Similar to difficulties regarding maintenance and community access, schools often struggle to conceptualize the practical pedagogical use of their yards. Instead of developing specific strategies, Brussels Environment, Tournesol-Zonnenbloem, 21 Solutions, and the architects are focusing on demonstrating the “educational potential” and showcasing the opportunities created by these spaces. A representative from 21 Solutions noted that in some schools, teachers are accustomed to traditional methods and show varying degrees of openness to change. To address this, Brussels Environment aims to forge connections between maintenance and pedagogy, and to stimulate innovative approaches, such as using the yard for subjects like math or French.

Among the four case study schools, each has some form of existing outdoor education, though these initiatives are often limited to a few teachers rather than integrated school-wide. At School C, only one or two teachers engage in outdoor education. At School

A, two teachers use the local garden and make annual visits to Bois de la Cambre, though logistical challenges related to time and non-education design of the spaces pose difficulties.

Teachers employ outdoor learning more frequently at School B, with three to four classes and five to six teachers trained in outdoor education. Activities take place in the yard, garden, or nearby natural areas, but logistical issues, such as the need for multiple teachers for off-campus trips, limit the time spent on learning. The garden's small size also constrains its educational value, described by one teacher as "limited" and merely to "tide us over" (T2B).

In contrast, School D has developed a robust outdoor learning curriculum, largely due to the efforts of a dedicated teacher. The school's extensive garden facilitates a wide range of activities, including studying geometry using bird feeders, calculating volumes through rainwater collection, and learning about composting and medicinal plants. This comprehensive approach promotes collaboration and cultural exchange, providing opportunities for students from 42 nationalities to learn Belgian traditions and share food and plants from their own cultures.

The gardens leading teacher at School D developed over thirty educational tools to assist colleagues incorporate outdoor learning into their own curriculums. These resources include informational sheets on various plants and recommendations for utilizing outdoor space. Despite this strong foundation, a number of educators remain hesitant to conduct outdoor classes and often feel pressured to adhere to the traditional curriculum. However, the schools director reported that some teachers take classes outside, like French teachers reading poetry in the yard.

Many teachers expressed the potential for outdoor learning is difficult to envision at this stage, but they maintain optimism that with the completed space, "it'll spread, little by little, when they see the well-being, the benefit and the pleasure of teaching outdoors" (D1D). Teachers already practicing outdoor learning hope to inspire colleagues by dispelling perceived hurdles.

Others indicated a lack of confidence in their knowledge of the outdoors, leading to a reluctance to engage with outdoor elements. While some interviewees acknowledged that developing an outdoor curriculum can be intimidating and labor-intensive, they did not view these challenges as insurmountable. Many perceived the additional effort required as a potential deterrent for their colleagues, with one teacher highlighting the challenge of overcoming the ease and convenience of pre-developed curriculum.

Interviewees frequently emphasized the importance of building intentional spaces for outdoor learning, like an amphitheater, to encourage less traditional classes like theater and French to use the space. Concerns were raised about the need for covered areas, like a *préau*, to facilitate outdoor learning in Belgium's climate.

Other teachers noted that renovated yards will be "more conducive" to outdoor learning because it "will enable us to observe more things. There will be a whole ecosystem" (T1B). Another teacher imagined how "it's going to be great to start from the yard rather than something more hypothetical. Maybe the kids themselves will come up with questions, and we'll be able to bounce off their questions and start a science lesson" (T2C). For students, the outdoor environment offers a different learning setting, which is particularly valuable for those who speak French or Dutch as a second language. Outdoor learning provides alternative sensory learning experiences and a more relaxed atmosphere compared to the traditional classroom.

Challenges mentioned by interviewees include organizing the shared use of the yard during class time, supervising outdoor activities and keeping the students attention.

Teachers generally view their students as enthusiastic about outdoor learning, often attributing the drive for such initiatives as "a request from children" with students nudging less interested teachers (T1B). Children clearly express a strong desire for outdoor learning, citing benefits such as "fresh air," complaining that classrooms can be "too hot" (School D). Students excitedly recounted what they learned outside, like "calculating the perimeter of the vegetable garden." Other children mentioned the potential to learn about "nature" and "animals," and how "we could see lots of insects" (School D). Students did express hesitations about potential issues like insects and how "everything is going to fly away," but generally remained excited about the prospect of outside learning.

When asked about the most effective way to facilitate the integration of outdoor learning, most interviewees identified training as a key need. Brussels Environment prioritized the pedagogic use of the yards, recognizing that "it won't happen spontaneously," intentionally building in training to support and motivate schools (BE1). Every year, Brussels Environment, in partnership with Tournesol-Zonnenbloem, offers annual training sessions consisting of five courses. These sessions aim to "to overcome potential obstacles" and increase confidence by "continuing to raise awareness" through tools and opportunities "to create, exchange, and talk amongst themselves." A representative from Tournesol-Zonnenbloem described teachers as "a bit unprepared at first, and they don't feel too confident but once we show them, they're super happy."

Considering high turnover among teachers, Tournesol-Zonnenbloem is working on a series of pedagogical tools encompassing a range of subjects to ensure broader access to resources. One teacher recounted training sessions spurring their imagination, allowing them to “experience it on our own” by playing games they could recreate with children (T1C). Training covers various subjects, including the water cycle and permeability, and is designed to provide practical, hands-on experience, “to make the yard an integral part of the school and not just a place for recreation” (T2C).

A few teachers mentioned a desire for training sessions to be mandatory for everyone. One teacher hoped for “the whole teaching team to have at least one day’s training on the use of the yard from a pedagogic point of view” (T3B). Brussels Environment deliberately keeps these trainings optional, “We’ll say everything that exists, but we don’t impose it because it doesn’t work...It has to become a matter of personal interest” (BE1). Tournesol also hosts collective days in schools, aiming to reach more teachers, but acknowledging that it’s not easy for teachers to find the time.

VI. Discussion

During the co-creation process, how were expectations set and responsibilities communicated within the schools and between partners?

Inconsistencies emerged between the objectives of Brussels Environment and the motivation of the schools involved. BE focused primarily on ecological and climate improvements, while the schools were more concerned with quality of life issues. Although these priorities were somewhat aligned – such as in areas like heat and water management – friction arose during the design process. This tension became especially evident during budget discussions, with the conflict of the *préau* exemplifying the divergence between actors involved.

To mitigate the impacts of these differing perspectives, improved communication stands out as a crucial opportunity to reduce discord and better manage expectations. However, Opération Ré-création faced challenges in communication due to the significant differences in the character of each school, suggesting a uniform strategy may not effectively address the needs of all schools. Some teachers reflected that, in hindsight, a more comprehensive overview of the project's goals, timeline, and key stakeholders would have provided them with a clearer understanding and more realistic expectations.

Many interviewees highlighted confusion among the various actors. Those with a less direct involvement in the project, often perceived a lack of clarity among the actors, leading to an overall less positive view of Opération Ré-création. A few suggested that a diagram or list outlining the roles and contact information of the different actors could provide much needed clarity, potentially reducing the burden on 21 Solutions and Tournesol-Zonnenbloem, who frequently acted as intermediaries.

Several teachers and directors also expressed surprise and disappointment at the delay in the project's timeline. Many noted that the possibility of such an extended duration had not been communicated at the outset, although BE also did not anticipate these delays. Similar to the confusion between actors, those who understood the reasons behind the delays were generally less frustrated than those who simply observed the timeline being repeatedly extended.

Communication issues emerged at two levels: between Brussels Environment and the schools, and within the schools themselves. To address challenges with BE, presenting a more thorough and realistic overview of the project – including a map of stakeholders, and best and worst case timelines – could better prepare schools for the various scenarios. Comparing School B's long-standing custom of keeping teachers, parents, and student

informed, to the strained communication between the director and teachers at School A, suggests that Brussels Environment and Opération Ré-création could support the adoption of communication tools and standards to facilitate the best possible outcomes for each school under different conditions.

It's difficult to predict the long-term impact of these communication challenges on the implementation and overall success of the project. Nonetheless, even those with more critical views of the project consistently expressed enthusiasm and support for it, demonstrating a willingness to participate in maintenance and openness to using the renovated space in innovative ways.

In considering horizontal communication between schools, providing teachers and directors the opportunity to network between themselves at Opération Ré-création's annual convening provided space for school staff to learn together and among peers. Many interviewees also expressed wanting additional and ongoing opportunities to exchange best practices and approaches, finding inspiration from one another. These opportunities are key for maintaining motivation as schools adopt new practices and habits.

How is the feedback from the co-creation process translated into a strategic plan and implemented in the final product?

During the participation process, the extent and manner in which schools involved community members varied significantly. A focus on parental involvement reveals that pre-existing communication patterns and levels of engagement influences both the schools' efforts to solicit parental input and the families' willingness to respond. Parents at School B acknowledged that while they didn't participate in every opportunity, they expressed appreciation for the opportunities presented to them.

Among the four schools studied, the one with a more affluent student body had greater success in integrating parents. In contrast, Schools C and D, characterized by lower socio-economic statuses and a higher proportion of non-European immigrant families, faced greater challenges engaging parents. A teacher at School D noted that many parents were hesitant to enter the school, highlighting the need for additional support to minimize barriers. This presents an opportunity for Brussels Environment to address environmental justice concerns through a focus on equity by providing extra support to schools where parents face additional obstacles to participation. Such support is critical given the pivotal role that parental involvement plays in the success of green schoolyard initiatives.

Overall, the participation process was perceived as successful by directors, students, teachers, and parents, all of whom provided overwhelmingly positive feedback. The

collaborative approach was evident in the various strategies employed, all of which contributed to the success of the co-creation. The process began with an emphasis on raising awareness and fostering a shared vision, which helped build a collective sensitivity to climate and quality of life concerns, laying the groundwork for effective collaboration between students and teachers. As the process progressed, presenting examples helped to reconcile initial differences in ambition.

Interviewees consistently reported feeling genuinely heard. The regular dialogue between schools and architects in developing the final plan fostered a genuine exchange of ideas, rather than a one-sided process.

We could conclude that the process successfully avoided token participation by ensuring that children were actively involved in both problem identification – an aspect emphasized by Hart (1997) – and in the iterative revisions between the school and architects. By creating on-going opportunities for participation, not only for children but also the broader school community, schoolyards can evolve into representative spaces that enhance a sense of place. This approach ultimately establishes safeguards to ensure that these spaces remain children's places, rather than places for children.

What key knowledge and skills do schools need to effectively manage and maintain their schoolyard?

Looking forward to the future potential for the schoolyards, we can consider what strategies to implement, ensuring success of Opération Ré-création schoolyards.

Many interviewees expressed dissatisfaction with the lack of budget allocated for ongoing maintenance, a concern echoed in academic literature as a critical factor for success. Schools without the financial resources to purchase tools, supplies, and hire external assistance frequently encounter significant challenges in maintaining their greenspace. Given the investment by the Brussels Capital Region in constructing these schoolyards, it seems inconsistent not to provide financial support for their upkeep.

Additional support mechanisms are in place to aid in the transition and maintenance of schoolyards, such as fostering community partnerships, which can compensate for budgetary constraints. However, many interviewees found it difficult to envision these partnerships during workshops with 21 Solutions, without a completed yard. It might be beneficial to consider integrating partners earlier in the co-creation process, rather than as a subsequent step.

Teachers often described the prospect of sharing their yard with external partners as daunting. The main outside partner at School B emphasized the importance of building trust between partners, a process that requires time. Vidal and Castro Seixas (2022) highlight that the planning process should be “place-based and place-conscious in a way that values local knowledge and is done with and for the local community” (p. 4). Engaging external partners earlier in the process provides time to develop trust, considering their priorities in tandem with the school rather than as an afterthought. Ian Mostert, project leader at IVN Nature Education, underscored the value of involving the community from the beginning, so they become “co-owner of the space” and “feel more response and take more care of the space,” which also facilitates coordination with maintenance efforts.

This doesn't imply that every community member needs a role in the design process – though some greening projects adopt such a holistic participatory approach. Instead, it is essential for schools to ensure that a few key partners are actively involved, which may encourage them to engage more willingly in maintenance activities.

Extending maintenance to the broader community can enhance local respect for the space, potentially fostering better relationships between the school and community, increasing collaboration, and reducing instances of vandalism or misuse. For instance an initiative by Less Beton in the St. Gilles neighborhood of Brussels successfully created a public greenspace. The project leader noted how their projects “are extremely well respected” because people know it's participative, creating a “dialogue with local residents,” illustrating how trust and respect can contribute to the success of greening projects.

Training is another crucial area identified by interviewees as a means to enhance knowledge and skills, addressing barriers such as lack of confidence and time. Many teachers expressed uncertainty about how to maintain their yard. The additional burden of learning and applying new skills, combined with teachers' heavy workload, poses a significant obstacle to integrating the yard into educational practices and participating in maintenance.

Teachers expressed appreciation for the planned trainings by Brussels Environment but suggested that mandatory training for the entire school could ensure a basis of knowledge across the board. Representatives from Brussels Environment indicated a preference for encouraging practices through incentives and self-motivation, rather than mandating them.

Although mandatory training may appear antithetical to the pillars of the participatory approach, it could potentially increase participation and project success. Addressing the gap in knowledge and boosting confidence among teachers to prevent entrenching imbalances in skills, causing unequal burdens of labor and burnout.

Training also provides an opportunity to set clear expectations for the school community, particularly regarding the unique nature of pedagogic gardens, which differ from traditional greenspaces. Specific training on the needs of school gardens is essential to prevent damage to intentionally messy spaces meant for pedagogic purposes. Including maintenance and cleaning staff in these training sessions can help develop a unified vision and adjust expectations, viewing messiness as an acceptable and purposeful aspect of the garden.

Finally, recognizing that schoolyards will remain somewhat 'unfinished' at the end of construction allows schools to adapt their spaces based on practical experience. Similar to presenting inspirational images during the co-creation process, showcasing examples of green schoolyards can help manage expectations and demonstrate that imperfection is a natural and encouraged aspect of these spaces.

How can the integration of the schoolyard into educational practices and community partnerships enhance its potential for broader impact?

Given that many students involved in the co-creation of the schoolyards may not experience their completion despite building a sense of ownership, it is crucial to establish continuous opportunities for new students to influence and engage with their environment. This ongoing involvement is essential for cultivating a sense of place. The inherently 'messy' and 'unfinished' nature of schoolyards can facilitate this by allowing students to partake in placemaking activities over time.

At School D, a conversation among students revealed concern over the potential loss of a mural created by former students during the transformation. This discussion signaled the significance of involving students in decisions about their environment, such as selecting colors, designing artwork, or choosing plants. This approach ensures that students appreciate their space as a continuum that honors past contributions while allowing for future enhancements. This reinforces the importance of leaving aspects of the yard unfinished, providing opportunities for future students to contribute, enriching their connection to the space.

There are several avenues for children to develop a sense of place and ownership within their schoolyard, through both the formal and informal curriculum. The pedagogic use of the green schoolyards allows for structured outdoor lessons and maintenance activities, which impart the necessary tools to respectfully interact with the greenspace, fostering trust and independence. For example, at School D, the garden's lead teacher educates students about safe and unsafe plants, fostering a responsible relationship with nature.

Students' requests for increased outdoor time reflects a growing desire to connect with their environment. For example, at School D, one teacher noted how students are the driving force behind outdoor learning, pointing to an opportunity to empower students to influence classroom practices by informing teachers in a reversal of traditional roles. Yet, for outdoor learning to be effectively integrated, institutional support of its legitimacy and educational value are essential.

Informal learning also plays a crucial role in fostering a sense of place, providing students with opportunities for self-directed interactions with their schoolyard. Playtime, traditionally viewed as time for kids to 'blow off steam,' is a vital space for kids to experience risk-taking and unrestricted play. The inclusion of loose parents, as emphasized by Blaire (2009) and Tranter and Malone (2004), further supports the benefits of informal learning.

The shift away from standardized sports fields is encouraging as it promotes student autonomy in selecting how to engage with their space. Allowing children to make daily choices, without feeling restricted by limited options, enhances their engagement with and ownership of the space.

Maintenance activities can take part of the formal curriculum, but can also be encouraged spontaneously to foster student's autonomy. Through an understanding of basic rules and guidelines, students can oversee their environment, discourage littering, and engage in activities like collecting loose wood chips. This empowerment strengthens their sense of place, increases confidence, and potentially leads to greater environmental stewardship.

Public activities and events provide opportunities for community involvement. Encouraging neighbors and parents to participate can reduce barriers to engagement, as suggested by a teacher at School D. While schools may have funding for some events, exploring additional avenues of funding for public programming could facilitate structured public access to the schoolyard to foster community involvement while maintaining a school's desire for safety and control.

Collectively, these strategies contribute to building trust, enhancing community ties, and promoting a greater appreciation for the environment.

VII. Conclusion

Reflecting on Opération Ré-création, we can appreciate its impressive feat of co-creating ambitious schoolyards with lofty climate and community impacts, while also recognizing its nature as a pilot project with room to grow and adapt with future iterations. To date, the project achieved an admirable participatory design process, providing children with a unique and impactful role in shaping their environment.

Moving forward, integrating continuous participatory opportunities will be key in nurturing a lasting sense of belonging and respect on the schoolyard. Ensuring children retain a strong voice in shaping their surroundings can drive transformative change, turning dull, monotonous schoolyards into vibrant, engaging, and educational environments.

Children offer invaluable perspectives that often go unrecognized, and their input can inspire adults to view their environments through a more playful and innovative lens. Respecting children's contributions serves as a powerful tool to instill students with a greater sense of civic pride, environmental awareness, and stronger sense of self.

As we strive to mainstream green schoolyards, it is essential to address the underlying challenges while staying focused on the needs of students. Children show consistent and persistent enthusiasm for outdoor learning and engagement with their environment, serving as a powerful reminder and inspiration for adults. At their core, the green schoolyard movement presents an opportunity to reimagine urban spaces with children at the center, to challenge traditional educational hierarchies, and to amplify students' voices in shaping their surroundings. By leaving space for children to lead, we can create beautiful and successful greenspaces, developing a deeper connection to nature and growing our collective environmental stewardship. As the green schoolyard movement progresses, we can be confident that as long as children's voices remain at the center, the kids will be alright.

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Brussels

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X. Annex

1 Neighborhood maps

Concentrations moyennes annuelles en dioxyde d'azote (NO2) (µg / m³) – 2022

Taux de chômage (%) – 2021

Revenu équivalent médian des habitants après impôt (€) – 2021

Niveaux de bruit multi-exposition : indicateur Lden (24h) (dB (A)) – 2016

2. Interview Guide

2.1 Schools

Introduction/Background:

1. Tell me about your role and participating in Operaciton Re-Creation?
2. What have you liked about the process of Operacion Re-Creation?
 - a. Is there anything you would've changed, or like to have seen done differently?
3. What is the overall goal of Operacion Re-Creation?

Participation Process:

1. How were the children & teachers involved in the design process?
 - a. Have you noticed an impact on the students from the project so far?
2. How did you feel the participation process went? Did the participative nature change your perception of the project? Has your perception of the project changed since the end of the design process?
 - a. Follow-up: What made the design process *feel* participative?
3. How did you feel after the first co-creation workshop? How did you feel after the more recent workshop with 21 Solutions?

Communication & Expectations:

1. How was the project presented to the school?
 - a. What expectations were set at the onset of the project during the appel a project and during the design process?
 - b. Were there any surprises along the way that you felt like weren't relayed at the beginning?
 - c. What was expected of you during the design process, and what is expected of you going forward in the implementation and maintenance?
2. How has your understanding and expectation of the final product changed over time?
3. How has communication been within the school about this? Has the experience been because of existing structures in the school, or because of the way the project was managed externally?
4. What is your understanding of all the stakeholders involved? Do you know who's working on what? Is this important to you?
5. Which stakeholders and partners have you communicated / worked with? Have you had any communication with other schools in Opération Ré-création?

- a. Have you had any direct communication with Brussels Environment, the architects, the commune? How often?

Future Governance & Management:

1. What support would you like to have follow you as the project progresses, and after implementation is complete?
2. Are there any obstacles you anticipating going forward in the process? (Construction, maintenance, etc.)
3. How do you feel about the possibility of opening the yard to the public? What resources would you need to support this plan?
4. How do you see the yard integrated in the curriculum? Do you think using the yard for pedagogic purposes will impact how the yard is cared for and maintained?
 - a. Are there any obstacles in using the yard for pedagogic purposes? What resources would you need to make this easier?
5. How will the additional responsibilities of maintaining the yard fit into what is already expected of teachers and school staff?
 - a. Do you feel as though the work will be distributed evenly?

Misc:

1. Schools w/ an existing garden: What was this experience like? What changes did you notice in the students? How is it managed? What are the challenges, and how are those addressed? How is responsibility shared?
2. If you attended an external workshop, like with Tournesol, was that helpful? How did you feel before / after? Would you like more similar workshops?
3. What would you define as a “successful” schoolyard transformation?

2.2 Opération Ré-création (Brussels Environment, Architects, Commune, Etc.)

Introduction/Background:

1. What is the overall goal of Opération Ré-création?
2. Why do you think this project is being implemented now? What kind of larger, institutional support is present to make it happen in this moment?
3. What do you see as the biggest challenges so far? What challenges to expect will come up in the next stages?
4. What do you see as some of the greatest successes so far? What has been most surprising?

Participation Process:

1. How are the architects involved? At one point did they join the project? Did they have any communication with the schools? With the kids?

2. How were the results from the participative process taken in account in the final designs?
3. How were the students involved in the process? Teachers? Parents?
4. Did you see differences in the level of ambition in the participatory process between schools? Why or why not?
 - a. For Brussels Environment / Tournesol: How did they sensibilize the schools before (refer to the game Marylou has)

Communication & Expectations:

1. How was the project initially presented to schools?
2. What kind of expectations were set related to timing, responsibility, workload?
3. How have responsibilities been divided and communicated between the different stakeholders? Specifically, in the maintenance, how are decisions being made between the schools and the commune? Schools that don't have support from the commune?
 1. For BE: If they weren't around, what would happen to the project?
 - a. Do you feel that in the schools, the project is relying on a few specific actors?
 - b. If so, how do you plan on integrating the new yard, and its responsibilities into the schools?
 2. Has there been communication between schools in Brussels and schools in other cities?
 3. How often do you communicate with the schools, and other relevant actors in the project?

Future Governance & Management:

1. What support structures will follow the schools once construction has finished?
2. For Tournesol: What are you seeing in the teachers as they come for training on educational use of the yard? Do they seem enthusiastic? Apprehensive?
 - a. Is there a difference in their perception / attitude before and after the workshops?
3. How is the project implemented differently in different types of schools?
 - a. How do they expect these difference to translate going forward, during and after construction, and with the long-term maintenance?
4. Is there a plan for opening the school yards after hours? What do you expect will be the biggest challenges, and how will those be managed? How important is this to the project?
5. Will the schools have to buy their own tools? Will they have to buy their own supplies, plants, seeds, soil? How was this communicated?

Misc:

1. How will this program evolve as more school yards are included and the project progresses?
2. What would you define as a successful schoolyard transformation?

2.3 External Stakeholders

1. What do you think are the biggest challenges in implementing green school yards?
2. What do you see as the biggest challenges in maintaining these yards?
3. The benefits of green school yards have been known for decades, why do you think we're only starting to see more wide-spread implementation now?
4. If you were to re-do your project, what would you do differently?
5. What differences did you notice in the school after the yard transformation?
Differences in students, teachers, etc.
6. Did you have experience working with schools whose transformation process wasn't participative? If so, how did that compare?
7. Do you have experience with schools opening their yards to the public outside of school hours? What are the challenges? What are the benefits? How do schools feel about this? What is helpful in making this a successful initiative?
8. What are the common concerns that schools have about these transformations and how are they addressed?